

Appendix — FLEXICO: Sustainable Machine Translation via Self-Adaptation

*Note: Sub-titles are not captured in Xplore and should not be used

This is the appendix for paper FLEXICO: Sustainable Machine Translation via Self-Adaptation, which provides additional details on the use cases used to evaluate Flexico and on the experimental results obtained. Specifically:

- Section I** provides additional details about the construction of the fixed test-sets for the En-Zh and En-Fr use cases;
- Section II** provides all the results for the specific FIPs of both use cases (En-Zh and En-Fr) on the 4 MT metrics (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi), 3 models (random forest, linear, xgboost trees) and FIP feature sets tested;
- Section III** contains the results for the generic FIPs of both use cases (En-Zh and En-Fr) on the 4 MT metrics (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi), 3 models (random forest, linear, xgboost trees) and FIP feature sets tested;
- Section IV** has the results for the leave-one-out cross-validation evaluation of the generic FIPs of both use cases (En-Zh and En-Fr) on the 4 MT metrics (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi), 3 models (random forest, linear, xgboost trees) and FIP feature sets tested;
- Section V** compares the system utility improves obtained by Flexico when compared against simpler baselines.

I. DETAILS ON THE USE CASES

A. English-Chinese Use Case

For this use case we used LDC’s ‘Hong Kong News Parallel Text’ [1], which contains news data from 1997 to 2000, and used chat-GPT to assign topics to each news article in the dataset, since this classification did not exist in the original data. To bound the output of chat-GPT, we created a list of news domains that we then sent in our query. The list of domains was the following: politics, business & economy, technology, science, health & wellness, environment, entertainment, sports, culture & education, social issues, travel & tourism, fashion & lifestyle, opinion & editorial, law & legal issues, finance, real estate & infrastructure. This list was created by browsing the news categories of multiple online news sites and by asking chat-GPT to provide a list of news domains. We then sent the following query to elicit news topics from chatGPT:

Identify applicable funding agency here. If none, delete this.

TABLE I: Sizes (in terms of number of news articles and sentences) of the En-Zh fixed test-sets.

News Topic	#Articles	#Sentences
Finance	172	2199
Environment	254	3295
Entertainment	50	764
Travel & Tourism	158	2514
Health & Wellness	112	1923
Sports	36	573
Governance	113	2131

```
CHATGPT_ANSWER_FORMAT = (  
  "1. Topic: value - Score: value"  
  "2. Topic: value - Score: value"  
  "3. Topic: value - Score: value"  
)  
  
prime_msg = (  
  "role": "system",  
  "content": (  
    f"You are a helpful assistant that classifies  
    news articles into topics based on this topics  
    list: [TOPICS_LIST]. Your output consists of  
    the top 3 topics and a number from 0 to 100  
    associated with each topic to allow me to order  
    the topics from most import to least important.  
    Format your answer as {CHATGPT_ANSWER_FORMAT}."  
  )  
)  
  
query_msg = (  
  "role": "user",  
  "content": f"Classify the following  
  article: `{article}`",  
)
```

After getting domains for all the articles, we isolated the articles of year 2000 (which was later used to test the FIPs), grouped them by the domain with the highest score and selected the domains with the most articles and that could be more different among each other to create the 7 fixed test sets shown in Table I. Note that Governance was not an original category and we created it by merging the following three categories: politics, Law and legal issues, and Business and economy.

B. English-French Use Case

Table II lists the Opus datasets that served as basis for the creation of fixed test sets for the En-Fr use case. Specifically, we see that some of the datasets (e.g. PhP and Quran) had

Fig. 1: English-French FIP fine-tune dataset. Each cell corresponds to a chunk of 10000 sentences that belongs to each of the opus datasets used for fine-tuning the base MT model.

very little data so they were only used for testing purposes. As described in the main body, we randomly ordered the chunks of each opus dataset to form a larger dataset with which we could simulate fine-tunings and create the FID. Figure 1 displays the random order of the random chunks in the dataset.

C. Feature Computation Cost

Table III displays the cost (in USD) of computing each feature-set to query the FIPs. This is discussed in Section V.C of the main paper and we see that using Flexico to prevent useless fine-tunings can save up to 80× the cost of a fine-tuning for the En-Zh use case and up to 40× for the En-Fr use case.

II. SPECIFIC FIPS

Tables IV, V, VI, and VII contain the experimental results obtained for the leave-one-out cross validation study of the generic FIPs for the En-Zh and En-Fr use cases, respectively. The tables show the MAE and PCC obtained for each fixed test-set, for each MT quality metric (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi) and model tested (random forest, xgboost, linear).

III. GENERIC FIPS

Tables VIII, IX, X, and XI contain the experimental results obtained for the generic FIPs for the En-Zh and En-Fr use cases, respectively. The tables show the MAE and PCC obtained for each fixed test-set, for each MT quality metric (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi) and model tested (random forest, xgboost, linear).

IV. GENERIC FIPS: LEAVE-ONE-OUT EVALUATION

Tables XII, XIII, XIV, and XV contain the experimental results obtained for the leave-one-out cross validation study of the generic FIPs for the En-Zh and En-Fr use cases, respectively. The tables show the MAE and PCC obtained for each fixed test-set, for each MT quality metric (COMET22, chrF, SacreBLEU, COMET22Kiwi) and model tested (random forest, xgboost, linear).

V. SYSTEM UTILITY IMPROVEMENTS

Figures 2 and 3 complement the results displayed in Figures 4.a) and 4.b), respectively, of the main manuscript by showing results for all the delta thresholds and fine-tune costs considered. We see that Flexico is consistently closer to the optimal oracle than the simpler baselines.

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TABLE II: Opus datasets used for fine-tuning and testing [2].

Dataset	Task	#Sents	Domain	Source
ELRC [3]	Test	1625	Legal	ELRC_1075_EUIPO - IP case law French-English
PHP [4]	Test	1754	Tech	Parallel corpus originally extracted from http://se.php.net/download-docs.php
Quran (Tanzil) [5]	Test	440	Religion	Collection of Quran translations
ELITR [6], [7]	Test & fine-tune	1774 — 359000	Legal	Derived from documents published by the European Court of Auditors
EU Bookshop [8]	Test & fine-tune	1022 — 405000		Corpus of documents from the EU bookshop
TedX-fr [9], [10]	Test & fine-tune	1927 — 233000		Crawl of nearly 4000 TED and TED-X transcripts from July 2020
TedX-fr_ca [9], [10]	Test & fine-tune	1495 — 10000		

Fig. 2: Scenario a — total cost incurred by each baseline as a function of: the fine-tune cost and the target delta improvement for MT metrics.

TABLE III: Cost (in USD) of feature set computation for a single FID sample.

Feature set	Cost-En-Zh	Cost-En-Fr
All	7.49e-03	5.06e-02
Basic	6.46e-05	1.82e-04
ContAware	4.82e-03	3.69e-02
MTQual	2.61e-03	1.35e-02
Basic + MTQual	2.67e-03	1.37e-02
Sent-overlaps	1.28e-07	2.36e-07
Embeddings	1.09e-03	3.98e-03
n-grams	3.73e-03	3.30e-02
Finetune duration	8.38e-02	4.80e-01

TABLE IV: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the specific FIPs for the En-Zh use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Entertainment		Environment		Finance		Governance		Health & Wellness		Sports		Travel & Tourism			
			MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC		
RF		All	0.0098	61.14	0.0110	92.08	0.0078	88.82	0.0025	95.62	0.0021	90.63	0.0046	76.31	0.0033	84.75		
		All + Kiwi	0.0102	61.73	0.0115	91.74	0.0082	88.61	0.0026	95.55	0.0022	90.73	0.0052	75.30	0.0033	84.51		
		Basic	0.0107	61.52	0.0096	91.88	0.0065	91.20	0.0028	95.15	0.0022	90.61	0.0042	74.98	0.0034	85.08		
		Basic + ContAware	0.0104	60.64	0.0096	91.50	0.0064	91.29	0.0026	95.06	0.0019	90.80	0.0052	74.41	0.0034	84.21		
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0105	62.65	0.0114	92.21	0.0082	86.75	0.0025	95.89	0.0025	89.91	0.0040	76.11	0.0033	85.60		
		Basic + MTQual	0.0100	61.47	0.0109	92.21	0.0076	87.11	0.0023	95.97	0.0023	89.49	0.0036	76.63	0.0035	85.66		
		ContAware	0.0066	48.79	0.0054	80.02	0.0106	89.26	0.0026	93.72	0.0018	89.37	0.0051	69.02	0.0039	80.31		
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0032	64.65	0.0040	95.66	0.0018	89.92	0.0015	95.00	0.0011	91.94	0.0020	79.90	0.0040	85.15		
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0064	51.67	0.0061	78.82	0.0120	87.87	0.0027	93.93	0.0022	87.84	0.0048	70.12	0.0037	80.34		
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0061	50.50	0.0052	79.84	0.0118	87.59	0.0028	93.75	0.0020	89.16	0.0044	69.07	0.0038	80.85		
		MTQual	0.0026	-13.14	0.0026	-4.65	0.0040	-48.10	0.0025	-9.08	0.0023	-18.69	0.0033	-16.65	0.0068	-28.18		
		COMET22	XGB	All	0.0106	60.62	0.0105	92.02	0.0076	87.80	0.0027	94.44	0.0028	84.05	0.0046	66.68	0.0039	84.36
				All + Kiwi	0.0111	61.25	0.0115	91.70	0.0085	87.18	0.0036	94.29	0.0032	83.24	0.0060	75.95	0.0038	83.12
				Basic	0.0110	61.87	0.0096	92.70	0.0063	88.54	0.0031	96.02	0.0030	86.06	0.0032	76.71	0.0044	75.46
Basic + ContAware	0.0110			61.13	0.0100	92.22	0.0065	89.22	0.0032	94.77	0.0018	90.82	0.0062	53.26	0.0041	75.05		
Basic + Kiwi	0.0111			62.43	0.0110	91.44	0.0091	82.35	0.0033	93.95	0.0028	86.72	0.0043	74.12	0.0042	77.58		
Basic + MTQual	0.0104			62.87	0.0107	92.36	0.0072	84.59	0.0032	94.44	0.0030	85.47	0.0034	74.49	0.0046	74.37		
ContAware	0.0071			45.19	0.0077	75.30	0.0098	87.90	0.0032	91.89	0.0020	87.80	0.0065	64.35	0.0041	74.60		
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0040			60.30	0.0046	93.84	0.0027	87.83	0.0013	93.22	0.0016	87.70	0.0023	70.78	0.0036	82.23		
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0070			51.57	0.0081	69.58	0.0119	84.15	0.0034	93.26	0.0028	83.56	0.0050	60.89	0.0040	79.52		
ContAware + MTQual	0.0063			52.48	0.0067	76.42	0.0119	84.61	0.0029	92.64	0.0020	86.62	0.0045	66.02	0.0039	79.55		
MTQual	0.0026			-2.18	0.0025	13.26	0.0044	-33.36	0.0022	31.43	0.0024	-5.80	0.0048	-7.05	0.0064	-19.26		
Lin				All	0.0246	37.82	0.0396	-0.81	0.0242	48.22	0.0198	31.34	0.0127	65.76	0.0061	89.45	0.0032	90.00
				All + Kiwi	0.0097	66.05	0.0079	95.68	0.0084	90.11	0.0072	93.11	0.0087	80.75	0.0183	74.96	0.0046	88.32
				Basic	0.0120	55.26	0.0096	94.90	0.0094	85.17	0.0036	78.91	0.0074	-14.63	0.0180	-27.00	0.0066	56.17
		Basic + ContAware	0.0105	66.10	0.0134	94.16	0.0085	88.22	0.0067	94.01	0.0120	56.24	0.0257	37.37	0.0078	74.41		
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0209	27.91	0.0064	92.32	0.0093	79.20	0.0056	5.73	0.0059	-28.57	0.0131	-19.47	0.0045	81.98		
		Basic + MTQual	0.0307	18.06	0.0497	-15.62	0.0307	21.05	0.0217	-33.74	0.0138	-23.96	0.0084	39.99	0.0078	39.39		
		ContAware	0.0075	13.65	0.0073	86.82	0.0106	77.86	0.0022	91.28	0.0016	86.04	0.0074	64.99	0.0114	63.60		
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0039	40.71	0.0110	65.16	0.0050	85.35	0.0024	56.64	0.0018	48.57	0.0031	30.08	0.0049	51.65		
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0025	69.39	0.0042	88.75	0.0076	81.10	0.0021	91.11	0.0018	87.16	0.0065	76.12	0.0128	62.26		
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0040	58.75	0.0090	64.83	0.0101	85.26	0.0015	91.35	0.0013	90.77	0.0051	88.35	0.0047	96.06		
		MTQual	0.0026	37.90	0.0046	10.18	0.0040	23.15	0.0049	28.85	0.0059	34.98	0.0188	48.64	0.0255	69.67		
		CHRf	XGB	All	1.3015	82.06	1.8930	96.13	0.8842	91.49	0.2022	96.76	0.2537	94.28	0.5269	91.58	1.3702	85.48
				All + kiwi	1.3364	81.84	1.9308	96.07	0.8346	90.37	0.1974	96.71	0.2619	94.80	0.5131	91.96	1.3405	85.36
				Basic	1.2658	82.64	1.7974	95.84	0.7460	91.58	0.1881	97.35	0.2903	95.07	0.3899	93.40	1.1682	90.54
Basic + ContAware	1.3152			82.12	1.7590	95.72	0.7172	90.38	0.2059	96.37	0.2282	94.59	0.5180	92.48	1.3578	85.51		
Basic + Kiwi	1.3167			81.94	2.0326	96.05	0.8913	91.65	0.1722	97.65	0.2998	95.33	0.4641	91.79	1.2645	90.94		
Basic + MTQual	1.2829			81.77	1.9499	96.12	0.8431	92.26	0.1775	97.73	0.2940	94.88	0.4718	92.38	1.3076	90.35		
ContAware	0.8969			75.34	2.5995	82.64	1.4417	84.37	0.2243	95.52	0.1861	95.13	0.5557	91.89	1.4532	82.25		
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.3249			84.20	0.6670	95.37	0.3940	84.88	0.2177	95.29	0.1699	93.91	0.6134	93.62	1.5285	85.23		
ContAware + Kiwi	0.9234			75.58	2.6765	82.51	1.5241	84.65	0.2157	95.93	0.2215	95.70	0.5595	91.19	1.4418	83.14		
ContAware + MTQual	0.8943			75.57	2.5793	83.30	1.5238	84.96	0.2236	95.90	0.2010	95.38	0.5676	91.28	1.4304	83.26		
MTQual	0.3383			-12.10	0.8182	-23.88	0.8014	-20.20	0.8950	-8.09	0.5223	-15.82	0.9048	-21.84	1.8838	-07.61		
Lin				All	1.2929	81.58	1.9174	96.35	1.0962	92.66	0.2395	95.62	0.4202	93.07	0.4186	91.50	1.2297	84.70
				All + Kiwi	1.3264	81.44	2.0017	96.02	0.8072	90.27	0.2501	95.49	0.3902	93.00	0.4250	91.69	1.2610	85.36
				Basic	1.1670	82.46	1.7862	96.35	0.9736	92.59	0.2125	97.03	0.3685	93.61	0.4590	93.18	1.0149	89.81
		Basic + ContAware	1.3251	83.74	1.9632	96.39	0.7553	88.87	0.2453	94.84	0.4014	90.42	0.4727	86.64	1.3052	86.52		
		Basic + Kiwi	1.3376	80.64	1.9825	96.15	1.0281	92.46	0.2086	96.64	0.4091	92.82	0.4797	89.86	1.1483	88.73		
		Basic + MTQual	1.3195	81.16	1.8725	96.02	0.8798	91.77	0.2030	96.96	0.3978	91.38	0.4476	91.32	1.1756	88.48		
		ContAware	0.9549	74.33	2.1203	79.55	1.4026	81.63	0.2806	94.70	0.3140	93.79	0.4540	89.86	1.3388	85.49		
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.3777	83.36	0.8781	91.77	0.3986	83.84	0.2517	93.81	0.2109	92.92	0.6390	88.34	1.3925	85.35		
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.9275	75.30	2.4080	81.99	1.5952	82.69	0.2465	94.64	0.4448	89.65	0.5183	82.89	1.3323	80.25		
		ContAware + MTQual	0.9516	74.97	2.0614	82.30	1.5635	82.02	0.2394	95.46	0.3848	91.77	0.5306	86.26	1.3651	81.12		
		MTQual	0.4334	0.81	0.8152	-12.98	0.6905	06.14	0.7360	-1.54	0.5333	-3.26	0.8348	-18.95	1.4902	-06.19		
		Lin		All	2.4429	69.37	7.0028	34.59	4.6614	10.23	4.0561	-12.44	3.7619	6.43	1.4253	41.16	1.2898	92.62
				All + Kiwi	1.5736	86.06	1.7068	95.70	1.9461	90.60	0.6751	55.01	0.5063	90.87	0.5218	71.95	0.8251	87.61
				Basic	2.0297	70.82	1.8097	93.96	1.5082	89.67	1.4454	-16.70	0.4298	51.04	0.8861	00.84	1.3179	58.50
Basic + ContAware	1.2713			88.47	2.2282	94.34	2.0430	89.92	0.4451	95.51	0.6439	90.55	0.4628	84.46	0.7274	88.74		
Basic + Kiwi	2.4374			48.98	1.5041	94.17	1.0727	87.75	1.6222	-72.30	0.4386	31.27	1.2873	-56.55	1.4629	32.54		
Basic + MTQual	3.1717			36.72	9.6014	15.28	5.0863	-12.32	3.8458	-52.58	3.5403	-30.31	1.0985	-10.17	1.3389	78.79		
ContAware	0.5671			61.99	1.1085	90.79	0.8213	92.12	1.0930	85.73	0.3859	91.84	0.4743	82.53	1.4373	82.10		
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.3349			55.04	2.0347	68.65	0.5316	76.93	0.8608	53.46	0.4463	75.29	0.7464	54.35	1.2638	54.12		
ContAware + Kiwi	0.2521			77.32	0.6423	91.79	0.4619	91.49	1.1642	82.57	0.4441	91.94	0.5215	78.48	1.0884	86.22		
ContAware + MTQual	0.3975			85.60	1.0020	83.16	0.4656	92.00	0.4841	90.94	0.2788	93.88	0.9011	83.74	2.4838	83.72		
MTQual	0.9901			27.16														

TABLE V: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the specific FIPs for the En-Zh use case and for the SacreBLEU and COMET22KiwimT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Entertainment		Environment		Finance		Governance		Health & Wellness		Sports		Travel & Tourism	
			MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC
SacreBLEU	RF	All	0.4513	-9.67	4.1386	79.66	1.0724	69.54	1.0675	80.82	0.7551	73.18	0.7358	65.25	0.7954	74.38
		All + Kiwi	0.5889	-16.31	4.2065	79.71	1.1478	69.09	1.1845	80.21	0.7897	72.54	0.7397	68.20	0.7454	76.90
		Basic	0.5245	-14.83	3.9908	79.69	0.5011	69.72	0.6638	74.2	0.3070	76.01	0.7121	63.47	0.6187	74.82
		Basic + ContAware	0.5120	-15.75	4.0466	79.81	1.1300	69.03	1.1402	80.94	0.8140	72.85	0.7518	60.46	0.7455	80.02
		Basic + Kiwi	0.6010	-15.99	4.2939	79.70	0.5124	67.50	0.6764	76.52	0.3523	74.87	0.7683	70.49	0.6535	68.37
		Basic + MTQual	0.4785	-6.68	4.2054	79.64	0.5325	67.30	0.6468	72.06	0.3145	73.25	0.6743	63.16	0.7170	70.35
		ContAware	0.4650	-9.94	4.2741	69.98	1.3669	65.17	2.0499	75.18	0.9647	65.99	0.9096	-44.19	0.9184	-2.71
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.4443	-13.61	1.5597	85.29	0.8352	31.07	0.4390	78.08	0.2933	64.67	0.5050	60.52	0.6144	65.75
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.4634	-12.47	4.435	70.58	1.3982	65.26	2.1243	74.11	0.9452	66.08	0.8520	-44.27	0.8850	-8.55
		ContAware + MTQual	0.3429	0.20	4.2815	70.93	1.1328	66.45	1.6874	75.71	0.8849	66.71	0.9553	-17.01	0.9285	41.66
MTQual	0.2384	37.15	0.4706	18.44	1.1186	-25.40	1.0674	3.96	0.4834	-0.737	1.1127	-0.474	0.9840	-10.62		
SacreBLEU	XGB	All	0.4949	-9.11	4.0058	78.86	0.9830	69.90	1.1256	68.80	0.7215	72.89	0.6591	67.39	0.9012	29.86
		All + Kiwi	0.6069	-14.08	4.0857	79.86	1.1069	69.76	1.4065	77.00	0.9411	68.42	0.6439	73.31	0.7550	40.29
		Basic	0.6700	-12.59	3.9185	78.86	0.5318	64.03	0.8456	75.55	0.4019	72.86	0.5145	70.46	0.5164	73.16
		Basic + ContAware	0.6579	-14.25	3.8573	79.84	1.0346	69.81	1.2539	79.20	0.8677	72.37	0.5525	70.00	0.6760	71.18
		Basic + Kiwi	0.6311	-16.46	4.2777	79.49	0.5603	62.29	0.9660	71.92	0.4172	70.61	0.6568	74.01	0.6056	65.31
		Basic + MTQual	0.5301	-04.96	4.2265	79.57	0.5729	59.56	0.7328	73.72	0.2551	74.08	0.6292	67.86	0.6301	62.99
		ContAware	0.5941	-11.48	3.9492	70.11	1.4202	63.32	1.3147	69.56	1.0642	63.25	0.8614	-28.95	0.9524	-16.15
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.4686	-16.72	1.5780	84.12	0.8028	42.89	0.6505	72.88	0.3503	58.98	0.5648	49.97	0.6457	23.38
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.4851	-01.41	4.2552	69.53	1.3207	64.61	1.5951	68.74	1.0140	63.10	0.7156	-28.16	0.9415	-18.44
		ContAware + MTQual	0.3762	06.59	4.0718	70.41	1.1933	65.55	1.0224	67.19	0.7849	65.16	0.9599	-50.25	0.9639	20.82
MTQual	0.2560	29.14	0.5425	14.08	0.9609	-02.85	0.8061	-04.42	0.3828	0.794	0.8350	01.51	0.8540	-14.86		
COMET22KiwimT	Lin	All	3.4864	11.98	12.2610	15.07	2.4845	02.68	8.5803	-58.65	3.3706	-07.55	8.5884	-31.57	1.4786	34.23
		All + Kiwi	2.5794	-05.63	3.2655	84.81	6.2742	51.78	8.2808	18.96	1.5673	36.49	4.4889	73.31	1.7998	44.16
		Basic	1.1463	-11.78	3.8732	84.01	4.5451	66.00	8.9053	65.51	1.8903	36.51	4.9800	54.48	2.3538	38.92
		Basic + ContAware	2.3252	-06.68	3.3868	85.34	6.7316	51.97	11.2210	52.73	1.8873	45.76	7.1211	35.87	2.2210	45.95
		Basic + Kiwi	1.2038	-09.51	3.8149	83.88	4.1696	66.50	6.6807	47.80	1.8231	20.78	3.5084	51.45	1.8235	28.49
		Basic + MTQual	3.8911	10.22	13.7753	21.57	3.6442	12.64	7.4655	-48.37	3.1398	-08.34	5.6612	-15.89	2.0023	22.87
		ContAware	0.4709	-04.21	3.0819	78.46	0.9458	58.84	2.4893	72.48	0.4134	64.99	2.0030	47.57	2.6343	43.86
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.6318	-06.67	3.7758	52.12	0.7622	52.76	1.5584	51.40	0.5532	50.32	0.6751	64.12	0.8542	25.13
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.7591	-05.60	2.2450	80.79	1.3426	56.14	3.1873	68.00	0.6999	58.61	4.0094	32.39	1.1261	47.40
		ContAware + MTQual	1.1344	31.43	02.31	71.02	1.3716	75.21	1.6866	57.51	0.2569	77.50	1.0122	53.32	1.6106	49.39
MTQual	0.9101	41.44	0.8251	26.42	2.9408	62.65	0.9900	33.59	0.6903	39.25	1.1218	17.90	1.3302	28.69		
COMET22KiwimT	RF	All	0.0016	40.04	0.0037	55.99	0.0023	64.05	0.0009	50.86	0.0018	27.00	0.0013	63.86	0.0018	62.82
		All + Kiwi	0.0016	38.96	0.0037	55.45	0.0024	62.52	0.0009	51.20	0.0019	25.27	0.0013	63.43	0.0018	61.93
		Basic	0.0029	10.64	0.0019	-68.54	0.0011	63.58	0.0006	39.95	0.0031	-56.63	0.0034	-11.35	0.0023	-18.52
		Basic + ContAware	0.0025	-0.68	0.0017	-34.25	0.0010	-53.86	0.0009	-00.82	0.0032	-52.48	0.0025	-06.16	0.0029	-12.26
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0018	35.08	0.0038	55.42	0.0025	63.78	0.0008	59.81	0.0019	30.45	0.0020	61.69	0.0020	55.81
		Basic + MTQual	0.0018	37.48	0.0038	55.42	0.0025	63.67	0.0008	56.13	0.0018	29.68	0.0019	62.43	0.0020	57.66
		ContAware	0.0026	-03.40	0.0016	-31.83	0.0016	-57.48	0.0008	00.78	0.0032	-48.42	0.0022	-11.73	0.0024	02.85
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0021	11.35	0.0028	-76.94	0.0020	-48.98	0.0006	00.07	0.0023	-57.83	0.0015	-04.19	0.0021	-06.01
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0016	31.34	0.0036	55.38	0.0020	61.29	0.0009	56.14	0.0022	-09.17	0.0013	63.25	0.0022	61.06
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0016	34.52	0.0036	55.73	0.0021	64.18	0.0009	56.33	0.0022	-10.05	0.0013	63.74	0.0021	60.36
MTQual	0.0018	47.70	0.0028	50.97	0.0018	43.28	0.0009	54.18	0.0013	24.06	0.0012	54.36	0.0039	60.17		
COMET22KiwimT	XGB	All	0.0017	36.61	0.0027	55.60	0.0021	61.17	0.0008	54.51	0.0018	35.61	0.0010	62.26	0.0019	67.06
		All + Kiwi	0.0016	39.02	0.0027	55.6	0.0021	60.51	0.0008	55.82	0.0018	39.03	0.0010	61.16	0.0019	66.78
		Basic	0.0028	11.37	0.0022	-62.05	0.0010	-09.93	0.0006	nan	0.0029	-54.74	0.0015	nan	0.0020	06.92
		Basic + ContAware	0.0035	-06.67	0.0016	03.99	0.0010	-18.04	0.0008	-01.73	0.0026	-50.86	0.0015	21.20	0.0027	-02.23
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0016	42.06	0.0027	56.67	0.0022	60.04	0.0006	57.16	0.0018	27.67	0.0012	59.75	0.0020	58.94
		Basic + MTQual	0.0016	44.70	0.0027	56.67	0.0020	59.08	0.0006	53.31	0.0019	24.93	0.0011	57.96	0.0019	60.92
		ContAware	0.0027	-06.66	0.0015	17.58	0.0010	08.61	0.0008	09.52	0.0034	-46.79	0.0015	-01.23	0.0021	15.12
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0025	-00.81	0.0022	-73.16	0.0018	-36.87	0.0008	01.82	0.0022	-55.75	0.0014	-02.28	0.0022	-02.15
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0017	26.24	0.0029	54.15	0.0019	64.78	0.0008	57.06	0.0017	44.65	0.0010	60.28	0.0022	59.07
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0018	23.26	0.0028	55.43	0.0018	63.33	0.0008	55.78	0.0016	45.50	0.0010	61.04	0.0020	62.91
MTQual	0.0018	40.36	0.0024	44.82	0.0019	51.80	0.0007	57.09	0.0012	33.15	0.0012	54.05	0.0033	60.48		
COMET22KiwimT	Lin	All	0.0121	07.83	0.0107	17.26	0.0060	-58.13	0.0010	60.44	0.0091	-11.11	0.0080	32.88	0.0161	-14.08
		All + Kiwi	0.0057	21.49	0.0114	-18.47	0.0099	-48.66	0.0014	52.56	0.0083	-21.86	0.0062	38.60	0.0155	-15.09
		Basic	0.0066	13.34	0.0074	-17.79	0.0052	-74.01	0.0027	44.53	0.0062	-54.70	0.0026	21.08	0.0064	03.54
		Basic + ContAware	0.0076	15.04	0.0101	0.63	0.0062	-76.09	0.0033	32.87	0.0080	-54.19	0.0025	09.19	0.0076	0.42
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0099	17.83	0.0103	-19.16	0.0093	-45.36	0.0009	57.69	0.0082	-17.61	0.0056	48.24	0.0138	-18.16
		Basic + MTQual	0.0142	04.60	0.0079	-28.76	0.0062	-62.48	0.0012	47.90	0.0076	-21.35	0.0056	46.02	0.0125	-16.92
		ContAware	0.0067	-28.36	0.0026	-69.00	0.0058	-52.59	0.0013	-06.59	0.0026	-62.41	0.002	-30.09	0.0122	-37.30
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0026	00.14	0.0034	-37.90	0.0034	-70.65	0.0010	01.02	0.0028	-52.94	0.0021	-12.74	0.0061	-30.38
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0019	48.98	0.0057	-44.27	0.0053	-32.86	0.0007	46.30	0.0031	-35.03	0.0010	61.75	0.0051	01.32
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0043	27.10	0.0051	-30.15	0.0040	-26.64	0.0005	61.16	0.0037	-18.60	0.0011	64.63	0.	

TABLE VI: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the specific FIPs for the En-Fr use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Elitr		Elrc		EuBookshop		Php		Tanzil		Teds-fr		Teds-fr_ca	
			MAE	PCC												
En-Fr	RF	All	0.0014	57.52	0.0016	57.42	0.0008	61.24	0.0010	61.50	0.0090	58.44	0.0006	07.07	0.0008	71.42
		All + Kiwi	0.0014	57.05	0.0017	07.92	0.0011	-00.32	0.0018	06.34	0.0063	42.98	0.0007	-00.36	0.0010	31.76
		Basic	0.0013	66.62	0.0020	10.43	0.0010	18.29	0.0012	01.73	0.0020	-10.47	0.0009	03.10	0.0009	17.41
		Basic + ContAware	0.0012	67.11	0.0018	-10.19	0.0011	03.14	0.0015	-00.97	0.0032	-13.97	0.0008	-02.68	0.0009	02.68
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0014	53.83	0.0018	05.17	0.0011	14.72	0.0012	04.86	0.0017	46.11	0.0009	08.40	0.0008	45.31
		Basic + MTQual	0.0014	58.16	0.0016	53.19	0.0010	65.65	0.0012	64.41	0.0027	59.69	0.0004	46.92	0.0006	77.01
		ContAware	0.0027	14.90	0.0024	-22.55	0.0016	-17.10	0.0010	-03.38	0.0104	18.88	0.0015	21.52	0.0011	-08.58
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0028	10.77	0.0025	-14.07	0.0019	03.03	0.0010	-05.25	0.0105	18.77	0.0015	17.00	0.0011	15.86
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0022	-08.58	0.0017	10.33	0.0014	-12.93	0.0014	05.00	0.0065	66.00	0.0008	23.50	0.0010	32.24
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0024	05.90	0.0016	53.88	0.0008	60.09	0.0011	65.02	0.0091	72.98	0.0004	54.23	0.0008	70.55
		MTQual	0.0023	07.95	0.0022	37.52	0.0010	57.52	0.0015	52.53	0.0033	20.99	0.0004	29.15	0.0009	64.64
		COMET22	XGB	All	0.0015	32.58	0.0015	55.99	0.0008	61.40	0.0009	58.24	0.0056	44.30	0.0005	18.76
All + Kiwi	0.0015			39.23	0.0017	11.70	0.0010	09.94	0.0014	-00.79	0.0049	39.13	0.0008	06.80	0.0009	18.26
Basic	0.0012			65.02	0.0021	10.03	0.0010	07.56	0.0010	00.81	0.0015	-16.04	0.0007	02.93	0.0009	15.85
Basic + ContAware	0.0012			57.32	0.0019	10.02	0.0011	12.82	0.0013	-02.73	0.0035	-17.00	0.0008	03.04	0.0009	-07.67
Basic + Kiwi	0.0013			48.73	0.0020	02.56	0.0011	05.75	0.0011	05.49	0.0019	42.46	0.0007	17.18	0.0009	29.27
Basic + MTQual	0.0012			61.07	0.0014	60.49	0.0009	61.54	0.0012	62.92	0.0033	43.25	0.0005	54.38	0.0006	68.48
ContAware	0.0024			13.56	0.0020	09.46	0.0012	-09.37	0.0010	01.66	0.0058	05.82	0.0010	03.17	0.0011	-18.93
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0025			09.19	0.0021	-15.60	0.0012	06.81	0.0010	07.04	0.0058	05.83	0.0010	03.17	0.0010	10.36
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0019			-17.90	0.0019	00.37	0.0011	-05.91	0.0010	02.60	0.0048	53.33	0.0008	12.94	0.0008	32.02
ContAware + MTQual	0.0019			-19.54	0.0014	59.69	0.0008	61.16	0.0013	53.04	0.0055	58.04	0.0004	43.96	0.0006	71.63
MTQual	0.0018			20.75	0.0015	57.30	0.0009	56.21	0.0013	50.71	0.0034	09.57	0.0004	27.70	0.0007	59.24
En-Fr	Lin			All	0.0021	63.90	0.0024	41.31	0.0024	17.63	0.0031	28.58	0.0129	36.02	0.0006	59.56
		All + Kiwi	0.0018	57.48	0.0039	11.89	0.0031	03.82	0.0048	21.06	0.0044	19.01	0.0009	31.11	0.0023	15.80
		Basic	0.0015	58.45	0.0030	-05.44	0.0012	-00.43	0.0010	42.72	0.0028	-23.07	0.0006	15.62	0.0015	10.48
		Basic + ContAware	0.0025	53.56	0.0033	08.06	0.0035	-02.00	0.0024	19.45	0.0035	-06.35	0.0006	22.29	0.0026	05.79
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0027	70.64	0.0036	03.22	0.0013	16.84	0.0030	49.25	0.0016	37.74	0.0007	23.25	0.0013	30.42
		Basic + MTQual	0.0027	81.20	0.0015	63.06	0.0008	63.05	0.0014	74.56	0.0096	67.86	0.0006	60.75	0.0011	65.06
		ContAware	0.0037	19.53	0.0037	10.63	0.0018	-03.64	0.0033	06.63	564945.2171	07.38	0.0014	08.53	0.0015	-03.02
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0033	24.96	0.0030	-00.53	0.0012	27.75	0.0026	-16.51	0.0056	02.51	0.0013	12.05	0.0015	-02.21
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0032	35.76	0.0025	11.27	0.0022	00.95	0.0027	06.38	714006.1306	07.38	0.0008	19.07	0.0016	07.06
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0036	47.42	0.0024	41.55	0.0024	15.70	0.0035	22.37	21901.6980	-07.38	0.0005	43.07	0.0015	27.67
		MTQual	0.0041	59.15	0.0016	61.90	0.0009	66.09	0.0015	58.24	0.0038	72.93	0.0004	59.94	0.0006	74.84
		En-Fr	RF	All	0.0874	40.54	0.3745	12.74	0.1323	31.94	0.1048	61.95	1.0928	54.13	0.0619	34.40
All + Kiwi	0.0764			50.79	0.2398	29.18	0.1371	-03.24	0.1278	17.27	0.7233	46.02	0.1051	06.77	0.1833	-26.25
Basic	0.0954			46.04	0.2093	28.29	0.1372	05.77	0.2102	02.16	0.3428	07.48	0.1063	-08.13	0.1442	-23.13
Basic + ContAware	0.0869			46.02	0.2305	30.93	0.1386	01.43	0.1264	36.68	0.3720	-05.42	0.1013	-04.29	0.1720	-24.59
Basic + Kiwi	0.0798			54.87	0.2236	25.51	0.1359	-06.45	0.1432	09.96	0.3232	47.29	0.0953	08.10	0.1654	-18.80
Basic + MTQual	0.0838			48.78	0.3630	18.28	0.1497	54.69	0.0944	65.22	0.4296	57.81	0.0651	25.24	0.1096	20.52
ContAware	0.2745			07.71	0.2968	-00.77	0.1752	-02.54	0.4114	07.56	0.9730	-00.56	0.2495	06.74	0.3192	-02.12
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2618			10.63	0.3074	-11.36	0.1709	-03.55	0.4247	-03.08	1.0312	-07.66	0.2425	10.19	0.3329	04.21
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0988			20.58	0.3482	-21.73	0.1359	02.23	0.1255	25.81	0.8426	43.03	0.1126	18.58	0.1694	-06.01
ContAware + MTQual	0.1551			04.86	0.4568	-01.68	0.1335	33.77	0.1455	44.41	1.2017	53.87	0.0699	18.42	0.1038	34.81
MTQual	0.1350			17.42	0.4507	22.50	0.1379	26.12	0.1255	51.73	0.4717	36.62	0.0660	25.83	0.1294	01.56
En-Fr	XGB			All	0.0985	27.55	0.2597	19.58	0.1289	24.72	0.1102	62.64	0.7089	35.43	0.0647	45.63
		All + Kiwi	0.0852	46.00	0.2257	13.21	0.1474	03.22	0.1277	29.46	0.5657	39.97	0.1329	01.99	0.1853	-17.22
		Basic	0.1333	44.07	0.2129	25.49	0.1352	02.46	0.1469	-15.56	0.2314	-05.68	0.1259	-04.73	0.1539	-21.49
		Basic + ContAware	0.0953	43.69	0.2126	33.15	0.1407	-00.75	0.1358	13.82	0.4612	11.86	0.1161	-06.26	0.1823	00.28
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1054	48.57	0.2145	25.29	0.1407	-03.52	0.1449	17.18	0.2532	42.84	0.1139	08.54	0.1660	-22.63
		Basic + MTQual	0.0868	42.60	0.3010	00.16	0.1213	39.63	0.1076	59.17	0.4166	47.90	0.0699	38.61	0.1132	26.25
		ContAware	0.2375	18.72	0.2495	15.90	0.1734	-22.08	0.3805	18.24	0.7198	04.10	0.2026	02.79	0.2074	-03.94
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2363	13.37	0.2486	15.49	0.1660	-20.75	0.3724	-04.85	0.7364	01.79	0.1869	07.95	0.2020	04.83
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.1043	16.22	0.2804	-00.80	0.1388	14.73	0.1375	33.48	0.5212	24.96	0.1266	04.80	0.1667	-07.37
		ContAware + MTQual	0.1288	01.96	0.2691	30.56	0.1227	35.10	0.1828	30.85	0.7108	31.54	0.0650	47.30	0.1040	33.53
		MTQual	0.1132	07.96	0.2215	22.63	0.1272	17.67	0.1668	27.56	0.4970	23.19	0.1004	21.98	0.1419	-06.25
		En-Fr	Lin	All	0.2284	41.90	0.4376	13.80	0.3785	41.54	0.5415	35.12	1.3405	30.04	0.1096	48.13
All + Kiwi	0.1505			25.20	0.3603	-08.26	0.3950	25.58	0.3829	22.15	0.4415	02.64	0.1161	24.54	0.2809	-22.20
Basic	0.1008			52.53	0.2437	19.10	0.2580	15.16	0.4032	05.18	0.6187	-09.04	0.1653	-04.15	0.3276	-24.40
Basic + ContAware	0.1182			40.23	0.3354	02.82	0.5197	17.14	0.3916	16.90	0.5045	-15.00	0.1665	-02.84	0.2792	-19.15
Basic + Kiwi	0.1391			42.94	0.3672	06.46	0.1682	29.58	0.2448	07.22	0.3412	22.82	0.0772	37.74	0.3321	-28.00
Basic + MTQual	0.2643			58.71	0.2382	64.68	0.1455	58.95	0.3251	32.91	0.9790	60.50	0.1399	66.02	0.3173	20.08
ContAware	0.3349			-04.29	0.4995	06.58	0.1717	13.30	0.6531	21.51	56795008.1331	-16.40	0.2245	-02.83	0.3308	-11.50
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2924			22.47	0.4215	01.92	0.1590	-02.71	0.6028	-21.42	0.6337	-02.01	0.2233	02.12	0.3240	-17.45
ContAware + Kiwi	0.2076			08.23	0.3430	-10.43	0.1790	20.88	0.2673	17.73	77225788.7501	-16.40	0.1095	19.78	0.2520	-17.16
ContAware + MTQual	0.2233			37.62	0.5198	12.54	0.2085	43.04	0.4271	33.79	3477672.3442	16.40	0.0872	39.93	0.1	

TABLE VII: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the specific FIPs for the En-Fr use case and for the SacreBLEU and COMET22Kiwi MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Elitr		Elrc		EuBookshop		Php		Tanzil		Teds-fr		Teds-fr_ca	
			MAE	PCC												
RF		All	0.1821	52.22	0.6070	24.68	0.2525	47.33	0.3795	33.55	0.7009	65.53	0.1037	22.42	0.2352	15.06
		All + Kiwi	0.1407	45.82	0.3684	-05.38	0.2174	19.86	0.1861	23.67	0.4563	33.73	0.1627	-12.55	0.2669	-16.17
		Basic	0.1211	39.58	0.3272	32.58	0.2198	05.71	0.2177	12.02	0.3506	-02.38	0.1573	-03.46	0.2190	-05.87
		Basic + ContAware	0.1412	34.64	0.3546	-06.99	0.2276	11.89	0.1798	33.61	0.4137	-02.38	0.1609	-08.39	0.2612	-14.51
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1334	55.86	0.3454	18.70	0.2182	20.82	0.1911	30.54	0.2303	58.49	0.1709	-05.38	0.2244	-09.81
		Basic + MTQual	0.1711	55.30	0.6225	29.99	0.2999	45.70	0.3712	34.63	0.4046	70.94	0.1018	46.33	0.2223	18.83
		ContAware	0.5934	18.24	0.3829	-14.95	0.3186	09.31	0.8886	03.04	0.7866	-04.90	0.2897	01.04	0.3253	07.33
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5624	16.51	0.3633	-01.29	0.3898	-03.81	0.9039	-11.45	0.8778	-10.64	0.2926	-24.02	0.3510	-06.18
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.1808	33.31	0.3985	-13.90	0.2335	19.00	0.1878	19.64	0.6793	35.26	0.1395	-25.08	0.2080	03.75
		ContAware + MTQual	0.2883	30.54	0.6237	13.74	0.2507	46.89	0.1444	65.97	0.7186	55.02	0.1085	23.80	0.2075	38.46
		MTQual	0.2600	32.26	0.7039	25.26	0.2831	40.75	0.1533	62.75	0.3512	46.58	0.0965	50.35	0.2374	38.47
		SacreBLEU	XGB	All	0.1711	53.47	0.4229	20.86	0.2022	44.43	0.4112	26.96	0.4200	46.80	0.1072	31.15
All + Kiwi	0.1372			41.67	0.3491	13.54	0.2284	14.14	0.1824	27.33	0.3981	36.49	0.2391	-11.13	0.2703	-05.37
Basic	0.1745			45.74	0.3211	28.95	0.2300	02.90	0.1922	-05.61	0.2088	03.14	0.1874	-05.87	0.2340	-06.94
Basic + ContAware	0.1378			33.65	0.3583	-06.40	0.2458	-02.50	0.1965	16.30	0.3427	03.11	0.1974	-03.52	0.2726	-05.51
Basic + Kiwi	0.1371			56.02	0.3377	13.16	0.2475	15.97	0.1996	14.17	0.2591	54.71	0.2285	-07.55	0.2348	-13.30
Basic + MTQual	0.1337			59.17	0.3781	10.80	0.2086	35.74	0.3780	30.46	0.2441	67.76	0.1111	37.90	0.1984	26.88
ContAware	0.5548			08.40	0.4111	-16.21	0.3257	-06.69	0.7955	-18.13	0.4136	07.27	0.2650	00.06	0.2905	04.11
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5149			-05.55	0.3394	15.10	0.2967	09.12	0.8688	-04.70	0.4422	01.84	0.3052	14.83	0.3028	-15.78
ContAware + Kiwi	0.1445			34.12	0.3607	-04.28	0.2526	10.11	0.2124	03.05	0.3896	39.87	0.1754	-30.40	0.2379	-07.75
ContAware + MTQual	0.1870			28.76	0.4961	05.63	0.2086	37.66	0.1967	42.26	0.4043	43.61	0.1280	09.52	0.2360	17.40
MTQual	0.1851			37.59	0.3948	15.18	0.2136	42.35	0.1702	58.55	0.3709	39.99	0.1258	45.68	0.2306	01.09
Lin				All	0.4789	46.65	0.7229	20.17	0.2013	62.98	0.9234	34.63	0.7736	45.92	0.1900	30.76
		All + Kiwi	0.3030	28.54	0.8847	02.09	0.2512	37.34	0.5576	23.91	0.4963	28.27	0.3342	14.69	0.3086	03.01
		Basic	0.2488	51.18	0.5475	06.71	0.2721	-10.48	0.7829	03.51	0.2884	-03.43	0.3472	-14.28	0.3082	-07.80
		Basic + ContAware	0.2444	44.85	0.5835	02.67	0.2895	27.62	0.6555	18.42	0.4165	15.39	0.4436	-03.47	0.3147	02.07
		Basic + Kiwi	0.3447	41.73	0.6557	10.63	0.2318	13.21	0.6056	06.49	0.2930	25.57	0.1975	21.83	0.2992	-07.15
		Basic + MTQual	0.5733	59.34	0.3520	56.94	0.1805	61.29	0.7249	35.34	0.6727	69.28	0.2747	43.42	0.4796	25.19
		ContAware	0.6226	00.35	0.7236	06.46	0.3965	27.50	1.1769	21.13	24873987.7997	-21.92	0.3524	03.84	0.4119	07.75
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.6052	24.18	0.4368	16.97	0.4516	-14.22	1.1257	-13.71	0.4490	-13.14	0.3384	-00.51	0.4259	04.72
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.4812	14.51	0.5110	01.30	0.3090	26.19	0.5688	16.82	22193794.0062	-21.92	0.1916	13.49	0.2899	09.52
		ContAware + MTQual	0.2990	41.30	0.4863	29.85	0.2697	49.35	0.6586	29.00	729107.4477	21.92	0.1656	24.77	0.2360	34.58
		MTQual	0.3104	60.76	0.6357	50.48	0.2745	64.47	0.2041	26.44	0.3778	73.85	0.1038	51.92	0.1825	54.75
		RF		All	0.0012	78.31	0.0026	52.40	0.0018	14.22	0.0035	28.05	0.0020	56.88	0.0003	54.76
All + Kiwi	0.0013			76.99	0.0026	52.27	0.0018	13.18	0.0040	19.77	0.0020	61.78	0.0003	54.20	0.0007	68.81
Basic	0.0011			81.40	0.0030	07.91	0.0014	13.50	0.0029	-19.47	0.0016	02.23	0.0010	-07.65	0.0012	07.10
Basic + ContAware	0.0011			81.30	0.0026	27.10	0.0017	-28.17	0.0035	14.14	0.0018	06.12	0.0005	-16.76	0.0010	00.06
Basic + Kiwi	0.0012			80.32	0.0036	43.12	0.0014	36.96	0.0037	20.50	0.0011	67.62	0.0007	63.27	0.0009	76.17
Basic + MTQual	0.0011			80.44	0.0034	48.44	0.0015	39.13	0.0036	28.67	0.0010	60.22	0.0006	52.57	0.0010	62.22
ContAware	0.0048			-05.08	0.0040	04.38	0.0025	-34.86	0.0086	11.31	0.0034	09.89	0.0004	-13.54	0.0011	06.14
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0048			-05.41	0.0043	-03.73	0.0024	-37.54	0.0085	11.99	0.0035	14.62	0.0004	15.33	0.0011	07.91
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0031			-04.00	0.0026	51.26	0.0019	05.79	0.0040	20.05	0.0020	66.06	0.0003	51.15	0.0007	68.96
ContAware + MTQual	0.0029			-08.29	0.0026	53.67	0.0020	03.46	0.004	16.43	0.0020	63.47	0.0003	51.82	0.0007	66.72
MTQual	0.0027			02.01	0.0032	41.41	0.0018	25.76	0.0043	22.62	0.0012	48.39	0.0004	37.45	0.0008	67.43
COMET22Kiwi	XGB			All	0.0013	75.14	0.0026	41.19	0.0016	-00.26	0.0030	24.12	0.0020	36.84	0.0003	56.96
		All + Kiwi	0.0013	71.05	0.0027	37.03	0.0016	04.80	0.0034	14.19	0.0021	31.83	0.0003	59.78	0.0007	73.30
		Basic	0.0015	77.65	0.0030	22.64	0.0015	13.88	0.0034	-46.53	0.0013	-14.34	0.0005	nan	0.0010	02.76
		Basic + ContAware	0.0013	74.77	0.0025	39.65	0.0016	-10.59	0.0031	13.56	0.0018	-09.35	0.0004	-20.50	0.0010	12.62
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0013	70.96	0.0033	37.89	0.0014	25.24	0.0032	09.62	0.0010	63.56	0.0005	63.27	0.0009	76.57
		Basic + MTQual	0.0013	74.92	0.0032	47.52	0.0014	33.64	0.0029	24.84	0.0011	53.38	0.0004	57.72	0.0009	63.43
		ContAware	0.0043	03.24	0.0037	-13.44	0.0026	-32.19	0.0083	07.21	0.0022	-07.66	0.0004	-07.72	0.0011	10.75
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0042	-11.57	0.0037	-18.90	0.0022	-30.43	0.0082	08.28	0.0022	06.60	0.0004	01.52	0.0011	10.24
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0028	-14.03	0.0026	36.65	0.0017	-06.71	0.0034	15.96	0.0022	42.94	0.0003	44.28	0.0007	69.67
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0024	07.71	0.0025	47.96	0.0016	-08.29	0.0030	11.32	0.0021	46.45	0.0003	51.26	0.0007	72.25
		MTQual	0.0026	02.68	0.0032	41.77	0.0015	20.32	0.0032	16.10	0.0011	55.14	0.0004	43.76	0.0008	69.25
		Lin		All	0.0049	68.82	0.0023	69.80	0.0019	31.78	0.0112	41.85	0.0045	48.17	0.0004	47.16
All + Kiwi	0.0050			70.16	0.0023	64.83	0.0020	29.28	0.0105	50.51	0.0053	48.72	0.0004	55.72	0.0011	43.43
Basic	0.0023			73.94	0.0041	19.06	0.0021	14.52	0.0044	40.09	0.0013	-14.58	0.0007	06.67	0.0012	08.52
Basic + ContAware	0.0028			68.57	0.0054	26.28	0.0020	-02.76	0.0052	34.23	0.0035	14.84	0.0007	12.51	0.0015	07.16
Basic + Kiwi	0.0058			86.16	0.0027	77.10	0.0019	61.00	0.0090	76.30	0.0022	74.12	0.0003	63.67	0.0014	76.33
Basic + MTQual	0.0051			85.94	0.0022	77.97	0.0019	41.82	0.0087	81.50	0.0023	72.72	0.0003	58.00	0.0014	80.87
ContAware	0.0067			10.69	0.0041	24.54	0.0034	-12.08	0.0151	21.65	348473.9762	11.76	0.0005	01.96	0.0016	05.92
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0061			12.33	0.0044	11.78	0.0028	-11.05	0.0129	24.09	0.0025	-02.94	0.0005	-30.42	0.0014	-04.21
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0054			40.86	0.0034	56.58	0.0018	23.81	0.0051	22.77	379450.0779	11.76	0.0004	51.84	0.0011	42.60
ContAware + MTQual	0.0051			41.24	0.0032	59.00	0.0018	28.21	0.0054	10						

Fig. 3: Scenario b — total cost incurred by each baseline as a function of: the fine-tune cost and the target delta improvement for MT metrics.

TABLE VIII: MAE and PCC of the G-FIPs for the En-Zh use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Feature Set	MAE	PCC
	RF	All	0.0044	72.76
		All + Kiwi	0.0045	71.31
		Basic	0.0048	69.40
		Basic + ContAware	0.0045	69.34
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0051	69.72
		Basic + MTQual	0.0049	76.62
		ContAware	0.0026	67.90
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0027	57.78
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0026	71.29
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0026	71.86
		MTQual	0.0035	17.04
		COMET22	XGB	All
All + Kiwi	0.0045			65.10
Basic	0.0040			65.31
Basic + ContAware	0.0044			60.25
Basic + Kiwi	0.0050			70.22
Basic + MTQual	0.0053			76.51
ContAware	0.0023			69.07
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0027			55.07
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0026			68.47
ContAware + MTQual	0.0032			68.48
MTQual	0.0040			18.06
	Lin			All
		All + Kiwi	0.0136	61.78
		Basic	0.0075	60.90
		Basic + ContAware	0.0141	61.64
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0066	68.30
		Basic + MTQual	0.0073	53.52
		ContAware	0.0062	57.25
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0045	44.28
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0059	56.33
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0063	46.15
		MTQual	0.0057	10.19
			RF	All
All + Kiwi	0.6415			57.88
Basic	0.5614			72.80
Basic + ContAware	0.6717			56.18
Basic + Kiwi	0.6202			66.08
Basic + MTQual	0.6056			70.69
ContAware	0.6958			51.42
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5648			55.50
ContAware + Kiwi	0.6424			53.65
ContAware + MTQual	0.5943			56.92
MTQual	0.7524			28.06
CHRF	XGB			All
		All + Kiwi	0.6979	56.96
		Basic	0.5472	69.74
		Basic + ContAware	0.7504	48.86
		Basic + Kiwi	0.5455	74.07
		Basic + MTQual	0.5739	69.38
		ContAware	0.7471	47.49
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5777	55.45
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.6743	52.12
		ContAware + MTQual	0.6908	44.17
		MTQual	0.8059	29.61
			Lin	All
All + Kiwi	1.0963			64.43
Basic	0.6292			62.72
Basic + ContAware	1.1079			64.51
Basic + Kiwi	0.6258			71.87
Basic + MTQual	1.2031			42.53
ContAware	1.3265			51.40
ContAware-no-ngrams	1.2906			33.17
ContAware + Kiwi	1.2834			49.45
ContAware + MTQual	1.4369			47.16
MTQual	1.3162			09.84

TABLE IX: MAE and PCC of the G-FIPs for the En-Zh use case and for the SacreBLEU and COMET22Kiwi MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Feature Set	MAE	PCC
	RF	All	1.0156	55.24
		All + Kiwi	1.1522	59.01
		Basic	0.6732	58.37
		Basic + ContAware	1.1031	56.94
		Basic + Kiwi	1.0263	41.83
		Basic + MTQual	1.4243	47.68
		ContAware	1.0664	52.30
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.6172	39.55
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.9828	47.83
		ContAware + MTQual	0.9920	53.02
		MTQual	0.8047	12.42
		SacreBleu	XGB	All
All + Kiwi	1.1084			58.76
Basic	0.6623			57.38
Basic + ContAware	1.2020			57.77
Basic + Kiwi	1.0439			43.34
Basic + MTQual	1.5072			44.38
ContAware	1.1257			50.65
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.6595			35.72
ContAware + Kiwi	1.0010			44.36
ContAware + MTQual	0.9409			53.46
MTQual	0.7512			11.52
	Lin			All
		All + Kiwi	4.9097	53.16
		Basic	2.9786	52.43
		Basic + ContAware	4.6970	54.23
		Basic + Kiwi	3.2661	52.89
		Basic + MTQual	1.1195	71.36
		ContAware	1.3521	59.12
		ContAware-no-ngrams	1.5146	35.42
		ContAware + Kiwi	1.3328	57.54
		ContAware + MTQual	1.2565	46.69
		MTQual	1.2566	42.22
			RF	All
All + Kiwi	0.0019			21.86
Basic	0.0013			-31.58
Basic + ContAware	0.0020			-18.62
Basic + Kiwi	0.0020			15.32
Basic + MTQual	0.0019			05.66
ContAware	0.0021			-20.12
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0019			-17.03
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0020			12.13
ContAware + MTQual	0.0022			04.03
MTQual	0.0019			16.15
COMET22Kiwi	XGB			All
		All + Kiwi	0.0017	30.58
		Basic	0.0012	-19.91
		Basic + ContAware	0.0018	-12.42
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0017	24.36
		Basic + MTQual	0.0015	19.84
		ContAware	0.0018	-00.55
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0017	-15.95
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0022	14.93
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0020	09.65
		MTQual	0.0017	17.89
			Lin	All
All + Kiwi	0.0043			-28.39
Basic	0.0020			-14.79
Basic + ContAware	0.0041			-25.70
Basic + Kiwi	0.0025			-23.04
Basic + MTQual	0.0024			-16.44
ContAware	0.0025			-15.52
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0027			-09.30
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0025			-19.30
ContAware + MTQual	0.0050			-16.56
MTQual	0.0036			-06.41

TABLE X: MAE and PCC of the G-FIPs for the En-Fr use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Feature Set	MAE	PCC
COMET22	RF	All	0.0020	03.12
		All + Kiwi	0.0019	09.42
		Basic	0.0013	02.87
		Basic + ContAware	0.0014	24.32
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0012	39.79
		Basic + MTQual	0.0013	29.90
		ContAware	0.0026	15.18
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0028	12.21
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0024	01.13
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0021	00.67
	MTQual	0.0016	00.02	
	XGB	All	0.0015	-02.64
		All + Kiwi	0.0015	11.32
		Basic	0.0013	03.74
		Basic + ContAware	0.0013	27.61
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0012	39.29
		Basic + MTQual	0.0012	33.72
		ContAware	0.0015	17.66
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0014	16.69
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0015	05.66
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0015	-00.61
	MTQual	0.0014	07.61	
	Lin	All	0.0020	05.76
		All + Kiwi	0.0019	25.18
		Basic	0.0013	02.51
		Basic + ContAware	0.0019	24.83
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0013	07.62
		Basic + MTQual	0.0020	05.26
ContAware		0.0018	25.11	
ContAware-no-ngrams		0.0018	24.83	
ContAware + Kiwi		0.0018	25.74	
ContAware + MTQual		0.0019	03.20	
MTQual	0.0019	04.50		
CHRF	RF	All	0.2474	-01.01
		All + Kiwi	0.2176	13.44
		Basic	0.1603	-01.39
		Basic + ContAware	0.2040	07.07
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1636	37.79
		Basic + MTQual	0.1982	05.26
		ContAware	0.3443	06.67
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.3892	02.69
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.2877	07.23
	ContAware + MTQual	0.2732	-02.43	
	MTQual	0.2002	-02.44	
	XGB	All	0.1618	-07.46
		All + Kiwi	0.1565	03.87
		Basic	0.1508	-00.90
		Basic + ContAware	0.1670	14.62
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1474	37.82
		Basic + MTQual	0.1700	11.68
		ContAware	0.1699	13.94
ContAware-no-ngrams		0.1893	-02.63	
ContAware + Kiwi		0.1657	02.83	
ContAware + MTQual	0.1632	-01.90		
MTQual	0.1726	-00.31		
Lin	All	0.2330	10.29	
	All + Kiwi	0.2435	5.24	
	Basic	0.1500	-04.22	
	Basic + ContAware	0.2339	14.03	
	Basic + Kiwi	0.2009	-08.10	
	Basic + MTQual	0.2380	-00.40	
	ContAware	0.2364	14.02	
	ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2247	05.59	
	ContAware + Kiwi	0.2517	05.07	
	ContAware + MTQual	0.2270	10.78	
MTQual	0.2563	0.46		

TABLE XI: MAE and PCC of the G-FIPs for the En-Fr use case and for the SacreBLEU and COMET22Kiwi MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Feature Set	MAE	PCC
SacreBleu	RF	All	0.2810	13.59
		All + Kiwi	0.2464	10.72
		Basic	0.2085	-01.59
		Basic + ContAware	0.2403	08.57
		Basic + Kiwi	0.2102	26.97
		Basic + MTQual	0.2333	16.56
		ContAware	0.4918	18.92
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5010	18.19
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.3139	10.25
		ContAware + MTQual	0.3054	10.21
	MTQual	0.2453	03.40	
	XGB	All	0.2666	11.09
		All + Kiwi	0.2568	11.38
		Basic	0.2139	-01.74
		Basic + ContAware	0.2328	18.57
		Basic + Kiwi	0.2110	27.33
		Basic + MTQual	0.2174	15.08
		ContAware	0.3226	18.15
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.3308	09.94
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.2669	12.31
		ContAware + MTQual	0.2572	15.25
	MTQual	0.2342	05.74	
	Lin	All	0.3381	26.64
		All + Kiwi	0.3749	17.92
		Basic	0.2361	-02.99
		Basic + ContAware	0.3563	24.50
		Basic + Kiwi	0.2726	01.81
		Basic + MTQual	0.3397	10.98
ContAware		0.3913	25.50	
ContAware-no-ngrams		0.3693	15.93	
ContAware + Kiwi		0.4049	17.90	
ContAware + MTQual		0.3268	26.90	
MTQual	0.3740	12.68		
COMET22Kiwi	RF	All	0.0017	42.39
		All + Kiwi	0.0017	42.22
		Basic	0.0019	02.12
		Basic + ContAware	0.0019	28.34
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0017	37.19
		Basic + MTQual	0.0016	52.06
		ContAware	0.0035	41.94
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0036	41.88
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0019	28.66
	ContAware + MTQual	0.0019	20.69	
	MTQual	0.0019	19.60	
	XGB	All	0.0017	38.18
		All + Kiwi	0.0017	39.00
		Basic	0.0019	-19.94
		Basic + ContAware	0.0019	25.42
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0019	25.64
		Basic + MTQual	0.0016	49.44
		ContAware	0.0029	32.45
ContAware-no-ngrams		0.0029	36.31	
ContAware + Kiwi		0.0020	16.30	
ContAware + MTQual	0.0021	-00.78		
MTQual	0.0020	13.58		
Lin	All	0.0026	47.12	
	All + Kiwi	0.0028	49.39	
	Basic	0.0023	20.20	
	Basic + ContAware	0.0028	32.30	
	Basic + Kiwi	0.0022	41.73	
	Basic + MTQual	0.0028	45.93	
	ContAware	0.0036	26.97	
	ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0035	17.24	
	ContAware + Kiwi	0.0032	46.42	
	ContAware + MTQual	0.0028	35.30	
MTQual	0.0028	40.33		

TABLE XII: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC), resp., of the generic FIPs when each dataset is left-out of the training set, for the En-Zh use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Entertainment		Environment		Finance		Governance		Health & Wellness		Sports		Travel & Tourism	
			MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC
RF		All	0.0065	57.89	0.0038	88.98	0.0033	88.27	0.0076	92.67	0.0056	90.68	0.0051	85.85	0.0040	77.44
		All + Kiwi	0.0063	56.98	0.0048	90.32	0.0038	90.50	0.0075	92.90	0.0073	89.12	0.0049	85.82	0.0039	77.20
		Basic	0.0062	61.39	0.0044	88.71	0.0040	86.20	0.0070	92.55	0.0075	90.05	0.0056	86.67	0.0031	84.25
		Basic + ContAware	0.0064	60.81	0.0041	89.70	0.0040	88.69	0.0087	91.98	0.0086	88.66	0.0051	84.69	0.0039	75.33
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0054	60.13	0.0059	84.84	0.0026	84.61	0.0045	92.66	0.0082	91.31	0.0072	86.10	0.0050	83.50
		Basic + MTQual	0.0069	59.64	0.0029	83.98	0.0026	80.96	0.0045	94.16	0.0062	90.65	0.0075	86.15	0.0060	83.72
		ContAware	0.0049	67.02	0.0026	93.82	0.0025	94.41	0.0034	76.62	0.0019	87.22	0.0015	86.96	0.0043	85.53
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020	65.02	0.0016	95.62	0.0009	94.01	0.0038	94.44	0.0041	92.25	0.0015	86.39	0.0063	85.87
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0043	65.58	0.0031	94.11	0.0023	94.27	0.0039	62.46	0.0020	91.21	0.0017	85.42	0.0045	86.76
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0035	67.15	0.0027	93.10	0.0023	94.57	0.0040	65.07	0.0019	91.08	0.0016	86.16	0.0038	84.96
		MTQual	0.0038	13.51	0.0025	17.06	0.0026	16.42	0.0024	11.38	0.0028	21.25	0.0038	07.80	0.0062	09.54
		COMET22	XGB	All	0.0058	64.17	0.0051	84.91	0.0024	80.78	0.0078	94.50	0.0044	88.98	0.0047	84.01
All + kiwi	0.0056			56.03	0.0064	85.64	0.0033	79.48	0.0070	94.05	0.0058	87.74	0.0038	85.02	0.0042	75.40
Basic	0.0052			60.20	0.0047	87.02	0.0039	83.78	0.0065	92.00	0.0069	89.96	0.0054	86.69	0.0033	83.47
Basic + ContAware	0.0063			58.26	0.0054	89.26	0.0034	91.45	0.0077	94.21	0.0070	89.04	0.0041	85.00	0.0042	71.21
Basic + Kiwi	0.0059			58.55	0.0063	80.64	0.0031	88.83	0.0080	92.78	0.0081	89.44	0.0055	85.48	0.0041	83.14
Basic + MTQual	0.0076			50.51	0.0029	85.19	0.0023	83.03	0.0049	94.10	0.0057	90.24	0.0073	84.49	0.0063	81.19
ContAware	0.0066			61.96	0.0031	92.18	0.0038	90.78	0.0022	89.19	0.0018	86.44	0.0017	83.71	0.0053	79.51
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0031			61.72	0.0018	93.75	0.0015	85.52	0.0037	92.42	0.0038	89.90	0.0018	84.60	0.0058	84.25
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0057			59.36	0.0029	92.45	0.0028	92.23	0.0042	69.37	0.0029	90.46	0.0017	84.48	0.0046	78.63
ContAware + MTQual	0.0036			56.69	0.0017	91.77	0.0025	91.91	0.0044	51.32	0.0019	88.06	0.0018	85.42	0.0037	83.38
MTQual	0.0072			12.33	0.0026	05.43	0.0029	16.18	0.0027	13.47	0.0030	19.15	0.0047	12.06	0.0065	00.63
Lin				All	0.0065	26.99	0.0107	45.38	0.0058	40.63	0.0367	63.90	0.0369	39.91	0.0070	73.12
		All + Kiwi	0.0256	45.86	0.0147	64.86	0.0068	64.65	0.0232	85.23	0.0152	84.72	0.0046	74.76	0.0296	71.37
		Basic	0.0090	47.56	0.0094	76.17	0.0080	75.97	0.0085	86.79	0.0084	86.64	0.0053	84.48	0.0046	75.39
		Basic + ContAware	0.0088	38.20	0.0186	60.90	0.0084	67.43	0.0195	82.44	0.0149	85.02	0.0048	74.13	0.0291	69.72
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0055	49.53	0.0094	77.42	0.0074	77.52	0.0061	87.80	0.0075	87.30	0.0054	85.15	0.0053	76.49
		Basic + MTQual	0.0060	61.18	0.0157	73.27	0.0077	84.49	0.0054	91.66	0.0102	89.26	0.0056	86.50	0.0053	86.18
		ContAware	0.0309	33.93	0.0064	82.94	0.0036	88.93	0.0169	84.69	0.0072	86.86	0.0115	74.45	0.0196	78.18
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0184	38.41	0.0030	67.76	0.0031	47.84	0.0068	47.91	0.0035	45.63	0.0031	30.12	0.0051	46.84
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0398	37.38	0.0027	83.15	0.0037	88.74	0.0292	82.27	0.0058	85.37	0.0129	72.45	0.0215	77.37
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0313	57.88	0.0158	82.08	0.0155	88.12	0.0299	88.17	0.0087	81.00	0.0225	86.52	0.0051	90.93
		MTQual	0.0057	36.81	0.0033	37.28	0.0035	30.13	0.0166	34.01	0.0033	29.59	0.0051	31.46	0.0110	51.28
		RF		All	0.4863	87.63	0.1696	95.97	0.2626	95.59	3.5816	75.77	0.9808	86.35	0.4593	93.74
All + Kiwi	0.4315			87.66	0.1663	96.22	0.5353	94.79	3.6179	75.80	0.8632	84.86	0.4618	93.89	1.3803	92.09
Basic	0.8960			87.13	0.1784	95.30	0.2093	94.11	0.1768	94.33	0.9245	95.68	0.5988	95.24	0.7950	93.76
Basic + ContAware	0.4380			87.96	0.1715	95.97	0.5878	94.86	3.9327	78.84	1.0351	94.85	0.4607	93.74	1.3801	92.43
Basic + Kiwi	0.7989			88.62	0.1851	94.58	0.2564	92.93	0.3614	95.36	0.7850	95.36	1.1066	94.09	0.8681	91.25
Basic + MTQual	0.8635			88.08	0.1507	96.45	0.2343	94.00	0.2930	95.82	0.7631	95.56	1.0785	94.32	0.8519	73.25
ContAware	0.4072			86.92	0.1981	94.59	0.5680	91.27	3.7288	58.31	1.0523	93.14	0.5115	92.74	1.4758	91.06
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2623			86.39	0.1887	94.83	0.4377	96.00	0.4633	95.26	0.6197	86.90	0.5532	89.28	1.8174	88.01
ContAware + Kiwi	0.4031			86.49	0.1985	94.70	0.5269	90.44	3.4099	59.92	0.8166	81.66	0.5098	92.79	1.5002	89.54
ContAware + MTQual	0.4646			85.83	0.1891	95.02	0.2425	94.55	3.4313	60.22	0.8550	86.84	0.5121	93.00	1.4696	90.62
MTQual	0.8978			19.88	0.6018	22.28	0.6035	37.65	0.7731	19.35	0.5792	27.28	0.8224	20.77	1.5046	17.32
CHRF	XGB			All	0.6077	86.02	0.1767	95.29	0.3020	95.78	3.6333	69.76	1.0299	86.14	0.3420	94.03
		All + Kiwi	0.4120	80.92	0.1646	96.31	0.7128	94.21	3.4485	69.24	0.9072	85.27	0.4236	91.89	1.3871	91.34
		Basic	0.8756	84.63	0.2235	94.92	0.2892	91.70	0.6274	94.69	0.9882	94.27	0.6266	94.62	0.7277	92.78
		Basic + ContAware	0.4289	84.82	0.2171	95.93	0.6310	94.49	3.1354	75.74	1.1088	91.66	0.3717	92.22	1.2906	92.79
		Basic + Kiwi	0.8052	88.68	0.2159	93.13	0.2632	92.94	0.3151	90.65	0.8863	93.53	1.1387	92.26	0.7084	90.69
		Basic + MTQual	1.3596	81.62	0.1861	95.80	0.2598	93.71	0.3397	95.80	0.8916	94.06	0.8840	95.46	0.7404	78.51
		ContAware	0.3368	83.87	0.2597	93.44	0.7216	90.20	3.1658	52.98	1.3090	84.07	0.5491	88.42	1.2696	82.99
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.4250	82.43	0.2067	93.36	0.4125	93.48	0.6174	94.55	0.6555	85.40	0.5567	87.93	1.6852	85.19
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.3968	82.48	0.2253	94.49	0.5570	92.20	3.2444	51.01	1.2608	70.77	0.5138	88.55	1.2617	87.75
		ContAware + MTQual	0.7507	83.24	0.2322	94.90	0.2988	90.50	3.1005	62.47	1.1010	86.43	0.4851	90.43	1.3469	83.48
		MTQual	1.4985	10.50	0.6052	22.50	0.6912	24.31	0.6981	19.78	0.6349	20.09	0.7797	19.86	1.5575	06.16
		Lin		All	1.7703	02.25	0.8641	62.02	1.0688	64.72	2.2178	82.57	4.6592	35.57	1.5470	74.46
All + Kiwi	4.2076			46.08	1.2048	86.06	0.9176	91.98	2.6120	94.78	0.7953	93.91	1.6480	54.23	1.5182	73.38
Basic	0.6833			71.65	0.4498	70.02	0.4437	78.97	0.3906	89.01	0.5778	82.83	0.4688	85.58	1.4436	79.64
Basic + ContAware	3.1302			45.28	1.6709	84.13	0.7315	92.06	2.2038	94.20	0.8389	94.20	1.4856	51.17	1.4308	73.02
Basic + Kiwi	2.4533			69.07	0.4642	68.87	0.4066	79.89	0.6848	89.53	0.4980	82.66	0.4464	85.08	1.0640	78.01
Basic + MTQual	0.7655			79.52	1.9908	61.39	0.7721	82.43	2.5733	95.62	1.9495	85.37	0.4453	85.18	2.8915	79.92
ContAware	5.8912			-08.65	0.9877	84.50	1.2187	86.15	2.9332	86.91	0.9726	88.68	2.8067	38.65	1.3736	60.93
ContAware-no-ngrams	4.2173			52.60	0.9912	61.83	0.8794	35.07	1.9650	44.86	1.0120	31.24	0.8848	00.86	1.8160	49.73
ContAware + Kiwi	5.4418			-14.15	0.5940	83.77	1.1102	84.15	4.6959	86.77	0.7717	86.26	3.0684	06.74	1.6922	53.25
ContAware + MTQual	2.5498			09.81	2.3990	81.81	3.5792	79.43	1.9001	91.14	1.4178	82.15	4.9324	84.33	1.0864	67.79

TABLE XIII: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC), resp., of the generic FIPs when each dataset is left-out of the training set, for the En-Zh use case and for the SacreBLEU and COMET22Kiwi metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Entertainment		Environment		Finance		Governance		Health & Wellness		Sports		Travel & Tourism	
			MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC	MAE	PCC
SacreBleu	RF	All	1.4196	35.99	0.7204	73.74	1.3441	70.42	2.5802	82.88	2.4049	75.65	0.3908	80.53	0.4900	78.09
		All + kiwi	0.6247	-14.40	0.8849	75.14	1.1049	69.95	2.6676	83.60	0.7762	65.31	0.3923	80.80	0.6863	86.28
		Basic	1.4470	-10.32	0.5009	73.77	0.6365	68.69	0.4364	81.53	0.7165	72.39	0.7503	76.69	0.5392	82.87
		Basic + ContAware	0.5577	-13.97	0.8352	73.77	0.9806	69.04	3.6974	83.58	0.9437	64.92	0.3925	81.05	0.4150	77.75
		Basic + Kiwi	1.2902	-12.50	0.5172	66.45	0.6510	69.07	0.5881	79.76	0.8338	73.16	2.9660	78.80	3.6925	82.64
		Basic + MTQual	3.5530	-14.97	0.3804	78.27	2.1117	69.84	0.8623	-0.941	0.7699	75.51	2.6789	76.57	3.9100	83.11
		ContAware	0.3674	-0.84	0.4819	69.52	0.8559	69.10	5.4174	58.66	1.5684	77.05	0.5556	57.41	0.5149	64.44
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5655	-12.66	0.2977	76.87	0.7223	55.98	1.2341	86.24	1.0838	57.70	0.5327	51.75	0.5881	37.36
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.3312	-0.46	0.4716	67.88	0.8251	69.29	5.4139	58.51	1.1631	77.58	0.5511	55.66	0.5103	61.03
		ContAware + MTQual	1.3764	01.04	0.3269	68.30	0.9302	70.79	5.3578	58.49	2.0429	77.86	0.5464	56.49	0.5192	63.87
		MTQual	2.2232	02.39	0.4328	46.98	0.7192	44.78	0.7870	-0.009	0.4438	27.36	0.5120	26.35	1.1132	26.89
		SacreBleu	XGB	All	1.8858	33.04	0.6422	76.93	1.0950	71.04	3.0708	82.66	2.3654	74.58	0.3699	75.61
All + kiwi	1.1311			-17.34	0.7710	73.72	1.2840	71.28	2.9364	84.22	0.7930	70.38	0.4219	72.63	0.4312	77.93
Basic	1.3824			-10.23	0.4832	76.32	0.6571	67.43	0.4431	77.45	0.6480	71.42	0.6989	74.81	0.4863	79.95
Basic + ContAware	0.7195			-15.83	0.8259	70.08	1.0739	69.09	3.3794	82.76	1.1885	65.30	0.4008	75.14	0.4110	85.82
Basic + Kiwi	1.7436			-10.78	0.4796	71.02	0.6469	67.66	0.5584	73.03	1.1228	74.44	2.0770	79.14	3.4383	83.60
Basic + MTQual	2.9448			-10.94	0.5843	75.05	1.9880	73.50	0.8114	-0.519	1.1153	76.29	2.8788	80.89	3.6937	83.99
ContAware	0.3024			-0.50	0.4744	62.72	0.8831	63.88	4.2216	57.58	1.3168	74.74	0.6063	31.74	0.7309	15.87
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.6936			-11.21	0.3219	68.03	0.8205	44.46	1.3188	84.43	1.3308	48.34	0.6059	31.39	0.6892	20.30
ContAware + Kiwi	0.2976			-0.57	0.5477	65.57	0.8426	65.14	4.7363	57.77	1.2136	75.32	0.5935	17.46	0.5227	67.53
ContAware + MTQual	1.7673			-10.54	0.3775	72.27	0.8416	62.01	4.4890	55.61	2.0621	76.64	0.6470	58.47	0.7139	31.85
MTQual	2.8446			-01.99	0.4396	24.06	0.7602	20.93	0.7944	-0.470	0.5716	14.59	0.6743	16.06	1.6826	26.50
SacreBleu	Lin			All	2.2983	08.53	1.0280	18.30	2.3787	74.18	3.4833	83.50	5.7264	52.92	1.3493	56.10
		All + Kiwi	5.8963	-04.78	4.3728	72.91	8.3118	55.50	1.9794	80.61	5.3198	48.65	6.1651	27.15	3.1335	51.50
		Basic	2.7373	-12.57	3.7887	68.19	3.0547	68.65	2.3415	85.56	2.9987	62.72	2.6858	59.45	3.3378	63.10
		Basic + ContAware	5.7692	-05.15	4.0744	73.87	7.8768	56.08	2.0600	82.08	5.1542	50.11	5.7930	26.70	3.0997	53.67
		Basic + Kiwi	2.0295	-12.42	4.1913	66.64	3.3211	67.05	2.9278	84.49	3.2856	60.14	2.8881	56.35	3.0178	60.21
		Basic + MTQual	3.3460	-09.22	1.1886	05.91	0.8205	80.61	1.0541	89.01	2.6599	74.42	0.6939	76.59	0.9518	75.33
		ContAware	3.5551	06.34	1.1132	76.69	3.5902	60.94	3.0040	77.62	1.0769	65.72	2.0997	09.72	1.7738	66.12
		ContAware-no-ngrams	2.1056	-12.01	1.7340	56.10	0.7870	33.46	2.5349	48.45	2.4592	30.92	0.8092	-28.86	1.5936	50.08
		ContAware + Kiwi	1.8786	09.06	0.9139	76.75	3.7156	59.60	4.0674	77.57	0.9638	62.71	2.3554	-16.48	2.1832	60.18
		ContAware + MTQual	4.6684	26.83	2.0505	81.53	3.9047	84.04	4.1426	84.20	3.5366	77.61	2.4456	45.22	5.5763	73.01
		MTQual	1.0105	24.24	0.7258	30.26	1.0353	37.96	2.5415	38.76	2.2811	30.84	0.9840	20.07	2.1623	05.58
		COMET22Kiwi	RF	All	0.0027	01.02	0.0023	-32.32	0.0027	-48.28	0.0021	-32.16	0.0056	01.85	0.0020	-00.36
All + kiwi	0.0026			00.40	0.0007	42.97	0.0025	-57.77	0.0033	-25.90	0.0047	03.92	0.0028	-19.15	0.0020	-31.60
Basic	0.0018			-12.47	0.0018	-71.32	0.0011	-58.97	0.0008	-45.58	0.0010	-46.69	0.0015	-24.91	0.0019	-24.18
Basic + ContAware	0.0018			-06.49	0.0014	-26.91	0.0026	-47.90	0.0023	-41.48	0.0014	-53.71	0.0022	-23.48	0.0032	-35.47
Basic + Kiwi	0.0019			-03.59	0.0032	-51.25	0.0027	-02.91	0.0036	-52.37	0.0058	05.20	0.0026	-16.84	0.0018	23.82
Basic + MTQual	0.0019			-05.24	0.0013	-49.48	0.0030	-74.70	0.0018	-41.34	0.0060	03.01	0.0024	-15.56	0.0026	-40.19
ContAware	0.0020			-09.24	0.0012	15.67	0.0034	-53.61	0.0028	-38.00	0.0019	-52.10	0.0022	-24.69	0.0022	10.63
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0017			16.04	0.0011	-02.14	0.0018	-41.59	0.0022	-50.71	0.0018	-34.59	0.0020	-22.33	0.0019	14.47
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0038			-12.17	0.0009	-16.27	0.0036	-46.61	0.0036	-34.89	0.0052	-10.38	0.0023	-21.50	0.0027	-23.60
ContAware + MTQual	0.0028			-09.74	0.0009	-40.89	0.0037	-50.05	0.0033	-35.92	0.0050	-29.87	0.0022	-05.73	0.0019	08.17
MTQual	0.0020			-03.68	0.0012	-34.16	0.0028	00.71	0.0028	-04.37	0.0058	08.82	0.0027	16.92	0.0023	-01.20
COMET22Kiwi	XGB			All	0.0037	02.60	0.0015	11.77	0.0022	-34.70	0.0028	-00.03	0.0045	-45.89	0.0026	-10.86
		All + kiwi	0.0033	00.18	0.0017	10.43	0.0026	-53.76	0.0036	11.05	0.0030	18.84	0.0040	-21.75	0.0019	-26.23
		Basic	0.0017	-14.14	0.0019	-64.56	0.0009	-20.64	0.0009	-30.49	0.0006	43.37	0.0013	-21.67	0.0019	23.80
		Basic + ContAware	0.0017	16.37	0.0012	20.58	0.0025	-16.54	0.0014	-34.03	0.0010	-43.34	0.0019	-13.81	0.0028	-10.31
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0018	-04.03	0.0010	-19.66	0.0025	-65.88	0.0032	-50.45	0.0046	-41.26	0.0028	-11.18	0.0018	22.57
		Basic + MTQual	0.0022	08.34	0.0011	-04.82	0.0025	-72.07	0.0024	-23.43	0.0047	-42.01	0.0028	-08.99	0.0021	-30.54
		ContAware	0.0018	09.40	0.0015	04.21	0.0018	-31.44	0.0019	-32.23	0.0010	-37.33	0.0015	05.14	0.0021	08.41
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020	17.52	0.0010	-01.80	0.0017	-34.62	0.0021	-47.66	0.0015	-43.96	0.0018	-14.78	0.0019	16.09
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0043	-05.48	0.0014	-40.00	0.0033	-40.91	0.0038	-27.92	0.0041	-48.33	0.0035	-26.69	0.0023	17.59
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0039	-00.52	0.0011	-33.73	0.0034	-47.00	0.0036	-38.50	0.0044	-46.46	0.0031	01.15	0.0024	16.28
		MTQual	0.0019	-02.24	0.0012	-08.17	0.0024	-25.96	0.0027	-02.62	0.0045	-41.60	0.0038	07.22	0.0021	-05.77
		COMET22Kiwi	Lin	All	0.0034	-20.48	0.0048	-43.42	0.0040	-55.43	0.0065	-36.00	0.0049	-41.52	0.0028	11.01
All + Kiwi	0.0076			-22.69	0.0035	-46.40	0.0068	-64.06	0.0070	-43.80	0.0043	-58.26	0.0055	-07.33	0.0025	09.35
Basic	0.0031			-25.20	0.0017	-40.98	0.0019	05.27	0.0022	-46.86	0.0015	-33.84	0.0022	03.07	0.0021	31.06
Basic + ContAware	0.0096			-21.73	0.0034	-42.69	0.0071	-61.24	0.0058	-44.75	0.0038	-53.48	0.0049	-06.32	0.0026	15.28
Basic + Kiwi	0.0035			-24.36	0.0025	-46.30	0.0024	01.26	0.0018	-48.94	0.0017	-40.12	0.0032	-02.62	0.0041	19.90
Basic + MTQual	0.0039			-23.77	0.0019	-28.68	0.0017	-07.34	0.0046	-34.98	0.0020	-28.22	0.0018	04.50	0.0020	32.35
ContAware	0.0038			-07.95	0.0014	-18.26	0.0049	-59.92	0.0062	-51.44	0.0022	-51.57	0.0034	14.02	0.0020	23.29
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020			-02.26	0.0017	-04.56	0.0031	09.06	0.0060	-05.50	0.0021	-00.67	0.0030	10.45	0.0024	-03.43
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0027			-09.68	0.0016	-23.22	0.0042	-64.00	0.0075	-47.01	0.0023	-53.55	0.0035	09.76	0.0024	16.94
ContAware + MTQual	0.0024			27.75	0.0088	-12.83	0.0055	-58.87	0.0034	-37.75	0.0017	-30.77	0.0054	24.58	0.0073	-09.97

TABLE XIV: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the generic FIPs when each dataset is left-out of the training set, for the En-Fr use case and for the COMET22 and chrF MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Elitr		Elre		EuBookshop		Php		Tanzil		Teds-fr		Teds-fr_ca	
			MAE	PCC												
RF		All	0.0020	15.74	0.0034	11.80	0.0021	-14.90	0.0074	-0.434	0.0024	-04.58	0.0007	-05.70	0.0009	24.72
		All + Kiwi	0.0028	05.58	0.0017	21.85	0.0016	-09.33	0.0060	-05.58	0.0018	-18.96	0.0011	-07.37	0.0011	-17.61
		Basic	0.0021	05.90	0.0018	12.04	0.0012	-17.90	0.0011	-01.84	0.0016	-22.97	0.0006	-04.86	0.0012	-25.49
		Basic + ContAware	0.0020	-17.61	0.0019	-21.42	0.0019	-26.26	0.0033	-04.13	0.0017	-20.72	0.0010	-04.70	0.0011	05.51
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0026	18.81	0.0017	-02.43	0.0011	02.82	0.0011	-11.09	0.0014	21.16	0.0008	-04.80	0.0011	-17.06
		Basic + MTQual	0.0022	12.71	0.0038	11.45	0.0026	11.27	0.0014	00.04	0.0017	09.90	0.0008	-30.02	0.0009	21.14
		ContAware	0.0024	-30.47	0.0023	-22.79	0.0046	-05.02	0.0089	-06.92	0.0019	-01.11	0.0036	04.53	0.0012	09.05
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0019	-11.04	0.0023	-08.87	0.0047	-04.24	0.0095	-02.30	0.0016	00.02	0.0039	03.99	0.0012	07.39
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0062	-00.77	0.0019	14.52	0.0012	21.03	0.0097	06.31	0.0022	04.33	0.0014	03.98	0.0015	-29.70
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0025	02.01	0.0080	-01.69	0.0031	02.42	0.0117	-04.44	0.0038	09.97	0.0007	-03.38	0.0010	03.78
		MTQual	0.0031	25.56	0.0053	-09.93	0.0027	11.45	0.0034	07.64	0.0034	06.80	0.0016	-29.94	0.0015	06.60
		COMET22	XGB	All	0.0019	nan	0.0020	11.41	0.0058	-07.29	0.0061	-10.17	0.0018	-04.82	0.0007	-00.67
All + Kiwi	0.0019			08.80	0.0018	-25.24	0.0018	-13.80	0.0051	-09.49	0.0015	-16.03	0.0046	-08.31	0.0012	-01.37
Basic	0.0019			10.21	0.0017	10.46	0.0011	-07.84	0.0010	-02.41	0.0015	-19.73	0.0007	-04.51	0.0011	-24.92
Basic + ContAware	0.0018			-12.09	0.0019	-19.32	0.0017	-23.41	0.0030	-05.84	0.0014	07.08	0.0011	04.12	0.0011	16.05
Basic + Kiwi	0.0028			23.65	0.0018	02.94	0.0010	13.52	0.0010	-13.15	0.0014	15.49	0.0009	-06.71	0.0010	-14.22
Basic + MTQual	0.0024			22.81	0.0038	10.33	0.0032	-13.42	0.0009	08.25	0.0018	04.79	0.0009	22.19	0.0010	05.94
ContAware	0.0019			-14.40	0.0018	-26.65	0.0024	-06.09	0.0037	-06.63	0.0014	02.23	0.0018	-03.27	0.0015	11.58
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020			02.49	0.0017	-01.88	0.0024	06.34	0.0032	03.07	0.0014	12.50	0.0018	-22.93	0.0011	11.09
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0015			nan	0.0017	nan	0.0021	22.40	0.004	-03.90	0.0015	12.31	0.0042	-08.02	0.0014	-08.97
ContAware + MTQual	0.0021			-10.94	0.0035	nan	0.0080	03.20	0.0091	-04.32	0.0020	02.36	0.0009	-10.35	0.0010	10.24
MTQual	0.0034			22.94	0.0045	09.69	0.0054	03.37	0.0014	-01.81	0.0024	nan	0.0007	-15.22	0.0011	10.73
Lin				All	0.0087	30.42	0.0076	37.48	0.0028	-07.83	0.0100	27.74	0.0216	40.40	0.0034	19.49
		All + Kiwi	0.0017	13.69	0.0030	-03.47	0.0019	-04.24	0.0037	19.39	0.0014	11.70	0.0009	14.32	0.0053	-09.98
		Basic	0.0025	08.94	0.0018	-01.48	0.0011	-14.69	0.0010	14.96	0.0015	-04.96	0.0007	06.58	0.0012	-23.28
		Basic + ContAware	0.0022	14.76	0.0028	-05.13	0.0020	-04.68	0.0026	19.87	0.0031	03.04	0.0011	08.71	0.0051	-11.00
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0044	12.24	0.0018	-03.32	0.0012	-18.02	0.0010	09.36	0.0037	11.90	0.0007	05.53	0.0012	-25.31
		Basic + MTQual	0.0035	37.58	0.0030	24.51	0.0026	-02.86	0.0020	21.62	0.0037	32.36	0.0046	12.43	0.0016	-06.66
		ContAware	0.0024	10.29	0.0030	-08.77	0.0012	11.82	0.0014	15.99	0.0032	00.36	0.0008	08.58	0.0037	12.30
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0018	-13.32	0.0028	15.69	0.0010	17.77	0.0017	15.95	0.0033	05.98	0.0006	23.83	0.0037	04.25
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0018	07.82	0.0032	-03.56	0.0012	12.29	0.0018	14.74	0.0014	16.05	0.0010	15.04	0.0040	14.98
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0081	21.79	0.0071	48.79	0.0034	07.62	0.0104	15.18	0.0206	40.75	0.0040	21.47	0.0034	38.24
		MTQual	0.0030	49.52	0.0026	44.05	0.0026	23.48	0.0018	23.70	0.0032	39.09	0.0052	10.59	0.0016	28.19
		RF		All	0.1523	-17.68	0.3013	-15.20	0.9624	12.06	1.1405	-07.03	0.2725	05.80	0.5578	08.32
All + Kiwi	0.2431			-42.24	0.3483	-29.79	0.1629	06.67	0.7782	-16.33	0.2524	00.68	0.3416	-06.08	0.1246	-00.30
Basic	0.0967			-37.04	0.3340	-05.66	0.1429	01.79	0.1242	-01.02	0.2370	-03.85	0.0968	-01.36	0.1560	-16.31
Basic + ContAware	0.2208			05.43	0.2891	-35.35	0.1694	03.40	0.4743	-31.78	0.2280	13.60	0.1092	-03.93	0.1273	02.81
Basic + Kiwi	0.2102			-42.01	0.4884	-32.12	0.1334	-06.39	0.1208	31.98	0.2834	18.72	0.1162	-09.27	0.1116	-00.12
Basic + MTQual	0.2382			-41.44	0.3064	-17.96	0.8920	07.26	0.1315	-36.38	0.2847	01.04	0.4460	00.17	0.1659	07.50
ContAware	0.1369			-03.43	0.3549	25.69	0.3463	19.03	1.1604	-09.89	0.4685	00.20	0.2848	13.34	0.1693	-02.67
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.1504			-06.46	0.3908	20.79	0.3394	-02.64	1.1923	25.35	0.4673	-01.72	0.1238	-14.06	0.2124	-03.00
ContAware + Kiwi	0.7496			-11.02	0.4197	-07.10	0.2094	-07.57	1.0876	14.29	0.5610	00.61	0.4198	11.01	0.1367	-01.06
ContAware + MTQual	0.1969			-05.41	0.2239	-05.12	0.8046	-08.75	2.1380	08.21	0.5865	-07.52	1.0043	12.81	0.1218	-01.77
MTQual	0.2744			-08.44	0.2291	-03.69	0.9182	10.69	0.1288	-11.68	0.4173	03.49	0.2431	-01.52	0.1095	-00.85
CHRF	XGB			All	0.0879	-07.73	0.3074	-23.59	0.3147	13.73	0.3546	-21.75	0.2813	07.37	0.0656	nan
		All + Kiwi	0.1124	-21.58	0.3152	-31.75	0.1376	01.44	0.5182	-19.42	0.2362	04.82	0.2097	-13.47	0.1360	-17.65
		Basic	0.1032	-05.36	0.3078	nan	0.1311	-00.50	0.1220	nan	0.2299	-02.30	0.0690	02.27	0.1318	-04.07
		Basic + ContAware	0.1294	11.95	0.2883	05.41	0.1303	16.94	0.1314	-13.62	0.2363	09.70	0.0713	-06.47	0.1368	-15.99
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1178	-37.24	0.4696	-31.95	0.1338	-07.72	0.1221	38.76	0.2652	19.72	0.0943	-02.61	0.1152	-25.36
		Basic + MTQual	0.1529	21.75	0.3038	-30.34	0.4271	11.64	0.1632	-13.54	0.2862	-09.51	0.1680	07.75	0.1688	11.15
		ContAware	0.1145	00.66	0.3217	08.57	0.1566	34.26	0.4768	-20.03	0.2956	-04.62	0.0957	23.01	0.1540	-14.01
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.1125	-05.82	0.3287	nan	0.1635	-35.62	0.3443	31.69	0.3001	-03.59	0.1078	00.85	0.1578	25.47
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.3262	-08.02	0.3115	-29.56	0.1417	08.86	0.4375	00.60	0.4092	nan	0.3828	03.79	0.1413	-02.84
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0879	-07.73	0.2717	13.37	0.5590	19.18	0.6244	-27.56	0.5390	02.38	0.0728	06.66	0.1111	nan
		MTQual	0.1498	-02.75	0.2487	-06.31	0.9010	28.70	0.1413	-13.23	0.3795	04.09	0.1849	-01.62	0.1200	nan
		Lin		All	0.2442	-23.21	0.3192	-00.59	0.2666	-26.19	0.3092	01.47	0.7160	13.14	1.1444	11.71
All + Kiwi	0.4021			-30.11	0.2296	-10.42	0.3907	-14.33	0.1911	-11.49	1.3300	13.55	0.1250	11.12	0.6194	05.02
Basic	0.1264			-32.54	0.2723	-28.70	0.1321	04.95	0.1208	15.18	0.2693	-05.77	0.0790	02.38	0.1121	12.70
Basic + ContAware	0.8395			-23.41	0.3259	14.14	0.5955	01.00	0.4750	-11.66	0.4459	07.99	0.3520	00.27	0.3143	05.61
Basic + Kiwi	0.2541			-37.55	0.3806	-31.02	0.1404	06.28	0.1232	06.42	0.3031	-09.05	0.1409	01.34	0.1172	17.42
Basic + MTQual	0.1380			-48.85	0.3943	-26.72	0.7105	-12.18	0.9222	08.80	0.7665	-14.85	0.6990	02.97	0.1198	-00.38
ContAware	0.7074			-07.87	0.2273	16.72	0.7169	-03.08	0.4220	-10.99	0.2451	08.76	0.5105	-00.52	0.1997	-03.62
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.5892			14.19	0.2183	24.94	0.9531	-41.13	0.2147	21.89	0.2232	18.54	0.1565	07.02	0.4308	00.41
ContAware + Kiwi	0.2749			11.68	0.2700	-17.56	0.3133	-21.04	0.1828	-10.91	1.1247	14.70	0.1869	13.94	0.5300	-00.67
ContAware + MTQual	0.1928			-09.89	0.2808	01.90	0.3057	-30.59	0.2615	-02.21	1.4585	18.29	1.1476	11.19	1.1595	09.67

TABLE XV: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of the generic FIPs when each dataset is left-out of the training set, for the En-Fr use case and for the SacreBleu and COMET22Kiwi MT metrics.

MT Metric	Predictor	Test set Feature Set	Elitr		Elrc		EuBookshop		Php		Tanzil		Tedx-fr		Tedx-fr_ca	
			MAE	PCC												
RF	RF	All	0.4161	-09.73	0.3792	-17.34	0.3658	00.60	0.9590	-04.75	0.3344	25.21	0.1409	24.37	0.7110	-08.50
		All + Kiwi	0.1830	-16.99	0.4348	-20.66	0.2342	03.54	0.2915	05.24	0.2604	09.58	0.1784	-02.80	0.1937	-05.58
		Basic	0.1629	23.06	0.4141	-32.54	0.2243	-03.34	0.1894	09.31	0.2065	-00.11	0.1137	01.04	0.1881	-02.42
		Basic + ContAware	0.1966	08.62	0.4249	-27.60	0.2412	09.31	0.3897	07.60	0.2813	04.28	0.1755	-02.11	0.2260	-05.46
		Basic + Kiwi	0.2164	-04.00	0.4666	-27.55	0.2362	-06.92	0.1869	21.34	0.2274	08.93	0.1168	20.26	0.1871	-27.64
		Basic + MTQual	0.5303	-08.86	0.3788	-13.46	0.2700	-16.84	0.8106	-05.04	0.3742	16.10	0.1094	-04.40	0.2383	-16.68
		ContAware	0.1898	14.46	0.5893	14.17	0.7430	18.17	0.8517	-05.01	0.5394	12.31	0.4778	-02.24	0.2832	09.79
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.2153	-01.03	0.6019	16.62	0.6961	21.31	0.8398	26.92	0.4969	06.28	0.5589	11.49	0.2977	-07.74
		ContAware + Kiwi	1.6878	-10.97	0.5476	-22.72	0.2772	-00.62	0.7083	02.85	0.6768	-05.16	0.2554	18.24	0.3269	03.65
		ContAware + MTQual	0.1556	01.23	0.3383	-03.47	0.8511	-02.38	1.0385	03.65	0.9607	-03.20	0.2930	16.29	1.0565	-07.04
		MTQual	0.4473	00.40	0.3386	01.76	0.2374	-12.25	0.7007	05.99	0.8466	31.00	0.1222	10.50	0.2358	-14.26
		SacreBleu	XGB	All	0.2575	-09.59	0.3901	-14.11	0.3658	16.45	0.2609	-31.04	0.5312	12.29	0.1427	24.93
All + Kiwi	0.1455			-13.35	0.4700	-02.020	0.2303	14.70	0.2094	-06.51	0.2768	-01.98	0.1441	11.30	0.2038	29.83
Basic	0.1329			nan	0.4042	nan	0.2255	nan	0.1927	-02.26	0.2222	00.06	0.1104	-00.33	0.1843	02.82
Basic + ContAware	0.1888			22.13	0.4838	-22.86	0.2514	16.89	0.1898	-08.06	0.2892	-00.47	0.1340	27.94	0.2200	01.39
Basic + Kiwi	0.1654			17.47	0.4654	-19.23	0.2660	-05.57	0.1924	16.68	0.2422	09.87	0.1673	-03.25	0.2006	-03.37
Basic + MTQual	0.1846			-00.48	0.3746	19.28	0.2810	10.31	0.3288	01.39	0.5592	13.48	0.1872	18.20	0.2066	-20.57
ContAware	0.1403			03.13	0.5712	-01.20	0.4306	09.61	0.3231	-16.39	0.3877	02.04	0.1257	15.92	0.2901	09.60
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.1591			-11.35	0.5731	-07.87	0.3914	26.47	0.2318	28.66	0.3564	-01.36	0.1157	20.68	0.3332	-04.60
ContAware + Kiwi	0.3821			nan	0.5589	-23.67	0.3120	-24.16	0.2595	-14.71	0.6211	-10.00	0.1857	-14.15	0.3078	20.67
ContAware + MTQual	0.1750			nan	0.3533	nan	0.7241	-04.87	0.2496	-27.46	1.0032	12.46	0.1276	14.42	0.7570	12.85
MTQual	0.2981			-09.29	0.3620	05.25	0.2221	19.78	0.4742	-27.22	0.7280	16.63	0.1938	29.46	0.2714	00.07
Lin	Lin			All	0.1558	-04.79	0.5775	-14.11	0.4462	-14.49	2.3257	32.40	0.2388	25.97	1.8280	-15.08
		All + Kiwi	0.1711	21.86	0.3784	-26.17	0.9279	01.97	0.7409	02.03	2.0901	23.99	0.1832	11.37	1.2578	11.06
		Basic	0.2291	21.24	0.3718	-27.04	0.2491	-10.94	0.1872	21.07	0.2435	03.70	0.1362	06.19	0.2262	-13.73
		Basic + ContAware	1.0266	26.08	0.5501	02.98	0.4305	05.05	0.5268	01.37	0.4270	19.08	0.4243	10.89	0.8895	07.27
		Basic + Kiwi	0.1454	08.89	0.4246	-27.78	0.2396	-09.38	0.1922	14.91	0.3695	01.74	0.2442	04.19	0.2082	-08.66
		Basic + MTQual	0.4705	-14.57	0.4984	-31.38	0.9650	-10.79	1.5737	26.51	1.6767	00.53	1.3751	03.29	0.2698	-12.94
		ContAware	0.5751	23.46	0.3756	15.55	0.8969	07.67	0.3476	-03.50	0.2913	17.98	0.9285	08.74	0.3986	11.98
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.7478	24.40	0.4392	14.53	1.2247	-22.79	0.2002	23.40	0.3691	32.38	0.4950	-05.16	0.7075	15.90
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.3502	19.88	0.6185	-21.81	0.5574	04.73	0.4294	-02.05	1.7818	20.64	0.5148	04.57	0.8705	14.91
		ContAware + MTQual	0.5664	08.98	0.4058	00.58	0.3752	-04.59	2.2058	26.70	1.4915	24.94	1.8708	-20.65	3.6077	-01.49
		MTQual	0.1648	-36.25	0.8713	00.46	1.3536	-08.43	1.5139	11.80	0.2849	-11.58	1.3741	-08.21	0.2536	-07.16
		RF	RF	All	0.0028	28.27	0.0051	26.09	0.0015	-15.39	0.0036	08.30	0.0017	04.94	0.0012	10.73
All + Kiwi	0.0030			30.48	0.0032	26.23	0.0014	-24.55	0.0035	-08.37	0.0013	-04.62	0.0010	16.37	0.0041	06.45
Basic	0.0031			-27.25	0.0027	-05.26	0.0015	-04.97	0.0035	09.79	0.0015	-17.39	0.0004	-08.42	0.0010	02.01
Basic + ContAware	0.0027			19.80	0.0031	-02.18	0.0022	16.82	0.0031	-00.69	0.0012	40.24	0.0004	10.88	0.0009	24.04
Basic + Kiwi	0.0028			28.43	0.0062	25.91	0.0028	-36.22	0.0038	09.04	0.0013	09.69	0.0009	14.36	0.0038	69.33
Basic + MTQual	0.0027			21.49	0.0072	27.07	0.0028	-22.17	0.0040	09.91	0.0016	-03.07	0.0018	-19.92	0.0042	46.88
ContAware	0.0020			06.08	0.0028	02.03	0.0066	-12.35	0.0030	-04.54	0.0014	-10.03	0.0015	-04.73	0.0011	13.72
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020			03.98	0.0028	09.58	0.0067	-02.03	0.0031	-08.31	0.0013	-32.43	0.0012	-25.05	0.0010	15.08
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0097			-09.61	0.0045	02.89	0.0014	03.66	0.0035	-09.88	0.0013	-09.74	0.0014	13.32	0.0041	11.06
ContAware + MTQual	0.0092			-10.51	0.0027	24.26	0.0015	-07.42	0.0035	05.60	0.0018	06.07	0.0013	10.23	0.0041	33.37
MTQual	0.0054			08.36	0.0027	09.81	0.0036	-38.29	0.0050	23.16	0.0018	-07.68	0.0018	-07.27	0.0035	45.95
COMET22Kiwi	XGB			All	0.0031	48.06	0.0052	20.16	0.0015	-21.07	0.0034	18.90	0.0016	03.55	0.0021	-13.70
		All + Kiwi	0.0030	57.10	0.0032	18.28	0.0014	08.98	0.0033	-03.94	0.0013	04.28	0.0016	-09.96	0.0046	58.06
		Basic	0.0031	-70.39	0.0028	-09.77	0.0014	-04.90	0.0035	-39.88	0.0016	-20.48	0.0004	-11.74	0.0010	01.67
		Basic + ContAware	0.0027	01.50	0.0028	02.98	0.0023	27.49	0.0031	-02.98	0.0013	-37.70	0.0020	19.98	0.0010	06.14
		Basic + Kiwi	0.0031	12.06	0.0061	26.07	0.0035	-28.40	0.0041	12.65	0.0012	03.64	0.0018	13.66	0.0039	69.95
		Basic + MTQual	0.0027	14.46	0.0070	26.58	0.0032	-04.10	0.0035	-04.09	0.0014	-30.38	0.0024	00.24	0.0041	67.08
		ContAware	0.0019	05.58	0.0029	-03.22	0.0042	-41.86	0.0029	-06.08	0.0033	nan	0.0038	22.70	0.0032	06.23
		ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0020	-16.34	0.0028	-00.08	0.0043	-01.32	0.0029	-09.80	0.0032	nan	0.0033	-04.80	0.0031	07.98
		ContAware + Kiwi	0.0077	-11.00	0.0038	01.99	0.0015	-06.67	0.0032	-07.37	0.0012	22.00	0.0025	-00.21	0.0042	46.34
		ContAware + MTQual	0.0079	-16.92	0.0026	28.52	0.0014	-10.37	0.0034	-20.08	0.0015	10.50	0.0019	-03.10	0.0041	44.32
		MTQual	0.0060	17.18	0.0026	18.85	0.0032	-16.42	0.0046	11.42	0.0017	-01.70	0.0011	-05.21	0.0029	44.22
		Lin	Lin	All	0.0027	15.50	0.0024	38.07	0.0033	30.45	0.0101	18.80	0.0055	15.09	0.0195	-08.79
All + Kiwi	0.0032			24.36	0.0030	30.58	0.0058	-03.20	0.0046	35.65	0.0095	03.16	0.0037	-15.71	0.0051	-00.37
Basic	0.0036			56.33	0.0028	21.59	0.0017	20.72	0.0037	30.87	0.0019	-16.08	0.0014	02.55	0.0016	-03.94
Basic + ContAware	0.0110			26.82	0.0035	13.15	0.0104	-03.48	0.0094	39.69	0.0064	-18.40	0.0027	-00.57	0.0024	-03.98
Basic + Kiwi	0.0016			57.89	0.0025	27.57	0.0016	22.91	0.0035	36.98	0.0057	-12.12	0.0021	03.63	0.0016	-03.36
Basic + MTQual	0.0049			52.21	0.0036	35.61	0.0017	24.07	0.0026	41.62	0.0116	-08.87	0.0131	-06.03	0.0020	05.59
ContAware	0.0070			-01.46	0.0030	02.76	0.0144	-12.47	0.0069	23.31	0.0110	-05.16	0.0068	-03.54	0.0052	-01.39
ContAware-no-ngrams	0.0042			-05.07	0.0028	-01.14	0.0086	20.15	0.0068	21.94	0.0096	11.27	0.0059	-30.79	0.0067	-04.09
ContAware + Kiwi	0.0059			09.35	0.0056	32.94	0.0038	-18.92	0.0028	09.60	0.0079	28.87	0.0014	-28.13	0.0017	07.10
ContAware + MTQual	0.0065			01.71	0.0026	25.71	0.0074	26.32	0.0102	-22.23	0.0202	32.98	0.0217	-18.61	0.0298	08.37